

EXPLORING MULTILINGUALISM IN RESEARCH

A survey to researchers at the
National Research Council of Italy

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Abstract

Between June and August 2024, the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG-CNR), with support from the Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS-CNR), conducted a survey on multilingualism and linguistic diversity within the scientific community of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR). This research, developed within the working group “Multilingualism and linguistic biases in research evaluation” of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), examined how CNR research personnel navigate multilingual contexts and how language influences scientific communication. The findings reveal a complex linguistic landscape in which the CNR research community regularly operates using multiple languages, with English remaining predominant in formal scientific communication. While the majority of research staff adapt without difficulty to international linguistic requirements, a minority reports practical challenges in expressing complex scientific concepts in non-native languages. The survey identified significant differences across disciplines, particularly between Social Sciences and Humanities (SH) and other research areas. This suggests that linguistic policies might be more effective when calibrated according to specific scientific domains rather than through standardized approaches. Despite these challenges, the scientific community views multilingualism positively, and the results indicate opportunities for developing appropriate linguistic support mechanisms and promoting institutional environments that recognize linguistic diversity both as an operational necessity and as an intellectual resource. The data collected in this research thus provide valuable insights for developing a scientific culture that integrates linguistic inclusivity as an essential component for the production and dissemination of knowledge.

Tra giugno e agosto 2024, l'Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari (IGSG-CNR) con il supporto dell'Istituto di Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali (IRPPS-CNR) ha realizzato una indagine sul multilinguismo e sulla diversità linguistica all'interno della comunità scientifica del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. La ricerca, sviluppata all'interno del gruppo di lavoro “Multilingualism and linguistic biases in research evaluation” della Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), ha esaminato come il personale di ricerca del CNR si muove in contesti multilingue e come il linguaggio influenzi la comunicazione scientifica. I risultati mostrano un panorama linguistico complesso in cui la comunità di ricerca CNR opera regolarmente utilizzando diverse lingue, con l'inglese che rimane predominante nella comunicazione scientifica formale. Mentre la maggioranza del personale di ricerca si adatta senza problemi ai requisiti linguistici internazionali, una parte minoritaria riferisce difficoltà pratiche nell'esprimere concetti scientifici complessi in lingue diverse dalla propria. L'indagine ha identificato differenze significative tra le diverse discipline, particolarmente tra le Scienze Sociali e Umanistiche (SH) e altri settori di ricerca. Questo suggerisce che le politiche linguistiche potrebbero essere più efficaci se calibrate in base ai diversi ambiti scientifici, piuttosto che attraverso approcci standardizzati. Nonostante queste sfide, la comunità scientifica considera il multilinguismo in modo positivo e i risultati indicano l'opportunità per lo sviluppo di meccanismi di supporto linguistico appropriati e per la promozione di ambienti istituzionali che riconoscano la diversità linguistica sia come necessità operativa sia come risorsa intellettuale. I dati raccolti in questa ricerca forniscono così elementi utili per lo sviluppo di una cultura scientifica che integri l'inclusività linguistica come componente essenziale per la produzione e diffusione della conoscenza.

Executive summary

The National Research Council of Italy (CNR) conducted a comprehensive survey in June-August 2024 investigating multilingualism and language diversity among its research community. The national survey was designed as part of the [CoARA Working Group](#) on “[Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment](#)” aimed at supporting “the EU (and other) institutions in fulfilling their duty to enhance, promote and uphold linguistic equity, diversity and non-discrimination in Europe and globally”. This requires fostering an academic culture that values diverse competencies, interactions and communications in all languages without exclusions or priorities.

The survey was conceived, managed and conducted by the [Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche](#) [*Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems of the National Research Council*] (IGSG-CNR). It garnered 910 respondents from a pool of 6,833 research staff (13.3% response rate) and revealed significant findings about language practices and attitudes in Italy’s largest public research institution.

Key findings indicate that the CNR research community primarily operates in multilingual environments. English is the dominant language for scientific publishing, as evidenced, e.g., by 581 respondents with Italian as their mother tongue publishing exclusively in English. However, language use differs between researchers in the Social sciences and humanities (SH) and the overall surveyed population, which includes respondents from SH as well as other disciplines (Mathematics, physical sciences, information and communication, engineering, universe and earth sciences - PE and Life sciences - LS).

The vast majority of researchers (92.6%) manage grant applications in non-Italian languages, demonstrating their capacity to meet international academic standards and engage in global research opportunities. Nevertheless, approximately 23% of respondents reported experiencing disadvantages in such a situation. This highlights a persistent challenge for a significant minority, who may face barriers such as reduced confidence, linguistic nuances, or the additional effort required to communicate effectively in another language.

Despite these hurdles, the overall sentiment toward multilingualism remains overwhelmingly positive, with 85% expressing that they view it as an enriching and essential part of their work. Emerging technologies are also beginning to play a role in addressing language-related challenges, albeit unevenly. The survey also revealed institutional challenges, particularly regarding language requirements for international researchers and the need for enhanced language support services.

These insights reflect a dynamic and evolving research environment where linguistic diversity is both a challenge and a strength. In such a context, this Report provides valuable insights for policy development and resource allocation, particularly in areas of language support, international collaboration, and institutional inclusivity. The findings represent an initial step in understanding the intricate dynamics of global academic engagement and local language preservation within research contexts. By examining current language use, attitudes, and challenges among respondents, this Report offers a strategic framework for fostering a more inclusive scientific culture.

1. Study focus: Multilingualism in research practices

Multilingualism is increasingly recognized as a cornerstone of global scientific collaboration, shaping how research is conducted, communicated, and assessed across disciplines and borders. On the occasion of [International Mother Language Day 2025](#), UNESCO has released a new report, [Languages matter: Global guidance on multilingual education](#), which underscores the critical importance of integrating multilingualism into education systems¹. Particularly in the field of science, the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) highlights the importance of multilingualism in the practice of science, emphasizing the need for scientific publications and academic communications to embrace linguistic diversity. This approach is crucial to fostering inclusivity, reducing language biases in research assessment, and ensuring equitable access to knowledge. In this context, the [Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication](#) stands out as a key example of efforts to promote linguistic diversity in the academic world. The initiative focuses on encouraging scholarly publishing practices that recognize and reward research conducted in multiple languages. It advocates for the development of tools and guidelines to reduce language biases in research metrics and rankings, ensuring that publications in all languages are valued equally.

Raising awareness about these issues is essential for promoting best practices in multilingual research and addressing systemic challenges. This expanded understanding of multilingualism serves as a framework for examining how national research communities manage linguistic diversity and navigate the challenges associated with it.

The [National Research Council of Italy](#) (CNR - *Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche*) represents an ideal case study for investigating language practices due to its unique position as the largest and most diverse research institution in Italy. Its extensive network of disciplinary institutes encompasses fields ranging from Social sciences and humanities (SH) to Mathematics, physical sciences, information and communication, engineering, universe and earth sciences (PE), and Life sciences (LS). CNR's interdisciplinary approach and international reach make it a microcosm of the challenges and opportunities faced by research staff worldwide in navigating multilingual environments. This diversity makes the Institution particularly suited to exploring how language dynamics impact research practices, from publication and grant applications to international partnerships.

Addressing language diversity within CNR not only offers insight into the Institution's internal dynamics, but also serves as a model for other research organizations facing similar challenges. Drawing on data from a survey of the CNR scientific community, this Report examines the role of multilingualism in research and presents some conclusive remarks aligned with global best practices and UNESCO's vision for a multilingual scientific ecosystem.

¹ The report provides concrete guidance for Ministries of Education and key stakeholders on the implementation of multilingual education policies and practices, with the aim of building inclusive and effective educational systems where all learners can thrive by learning in a language they understand.

2. Context: The National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

The CNR is the largest public research institution in Italy and serves as a cornerstone of the country's scientific and technological development. Founded in 1923, CNR's primary mission is to conduct, promote, and integrate interdisciplinary research activities that address both fundamental and applied scientific questions. It is structured into 88 research institutes that span the breadth of scientific disciplines, organized into seven overarching departments:

- [Physical sciences and technologies of matter](#)
- [Earth system science and environmental technologies](#)
- [Biomedical sciences](#)
- [Engineering, ICT and technologies for energy and transportation](#)
- [Social sciences and humanities, cultural heritage](#)
- [Chemical sciences and materials technology](#)
- [Biology, agriculture and food sciences](#)

Figure 1 CNR in figures

This organizational framework enables CNR to address complex research challenges in a comprehensive manner, integrating insights across disciplines.

As of April 2025, the CNR employs approximately 9,000 staff members (Fig. 1), of whom more of 8,700 form CNR's scientific community including 6,693 researchers and technologists: This data reflects a highly skilled and diverse workforce.

The research staff operates across a multitude of scientific domains and collaborates with peers in academia, industry, and government institutions. It actively participates in European and global research initiatives, contributing to large-scale projects and consortia that address pressing global challenges, such as climate change, public health, and sustainable development. The CNR participates in key governmental and intergovernmental thematic discussions, and engages with the higher education system, the business sector, local institutions, and civil society. In addition to its strong

relationships with various national and international academies of science and scientific societies, the CNR maintains a network of multilateral projects abroad and has established over 46 bilateral agreements with 33 countries. Regarding the 2021-2027 European financial programming, the CNR has 542 active projects, including 434 on Horizon Europe, positioning it as a leading body in Italy within this Program².

The linguistic landscape of scientific research at CNR represents an intersection of communication, collaboration, and global knowledge exchange. Multilingualism emerges as a strategic asset in this context, enabling researchers and technologists (hereby researchers) to transcend linguistic barriers and integrate diverse intellectual perspectives.

To gain insights into the linguistic situation at CNR in comparison with other institutions (Universities and other research bodies), reference may be made to the data (Table 1) concerning the distribution of outputs' languages submitted for the National Evaluation exercise 2015–2019³.

	English		Italian		Other languages	
	CNR	Other institutions	CNR	Other institutions	CNR	Other institutions
1 Mathematics and computer sciences	99.7	99.5	0.0	0.4	0.3	0.0
2 Physics	99.7	99.9	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.0
3 Chemistry	99.7	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0
4 Earth sciences	99.1	99.8	0.0	0.1	0.9	0.1
5 Biology	99.4	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.0
6 Medicine	99.0	99.9	0.2	0.1	0.8	0.0
7 Agricultural and veterinary sciences	99.2	99.8	0.0	0.1	0.8	0.0
8a Architecture	70.6	53.4	29.4	44.6	0.0	1.9
8b Civil engineering	98.6	99.8	0.0	0.1	1.4	0.0
9 Industrial and information engineering	99.5	99.9	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.0
10 Classics, Philology, Literary Studies, Art History	46.8	27.7	48.1	57.4	5.1	14.8
11a History, Philosophy and Pedagogy	45.7	28.4	48.9	65.6	5.3	6.0
11b Psychology	97.9	97.9	2.1	2.0	0.0	0.1
12 Law Studies	59.0	10.9	38.5	87.1	2.6	2.0
13a Economics and Statistics	94.7	97.7	5.3	2.2	0.0	0.1
13b Business Studies	66.7	85.7	29.8	14.1	3.5	0.3
14 Political and Social Sciences	50.0	47.5	48.6	49.5	1.4	3.0

Table 1 Distribution of outputs' languages submitted for the National Evaluation exercise 2015-2019

Notable differences emerge between CNR and other institutions, regarding the use of English in scientific outputs. In particular, several disciplinary areas show a significantly higher use of English in CNR outputs compared to those from other institutions. This is especially evident in Architecture (Area 8a), where 70.6% of CNR outputs are in English, while only 53.4% of outputs from other institutions use English.

² See CNR Reorganization and relaunch plan. Final Report, <https://www.cnr.it/trasparenza/delibere-cda/documento/128211/20250321-deliberacda-048-.pdf>.

³ Table 1 has been compiled on the basis of data kindly provided upon request by the National Agency for the Evaluation of the University System and Research (ANVUR), as part of the Italian Research Quality Assessment (VQR) 2015–2019.

Similarly, in Law Studies (Area 12), CNR outputs in English reach 59.0%, whereas those from other institutions are much lower at 10.9%.

A similar pattern can be observed in Political and Social Sciences (Area 14), where half of the CNR submissions are in English, in contrast with 47.5% from other institutions. While the difference is smaller here, it still reflects a stronger orientation towards English in CNR's output.

Another striking example is Classics, Philology, Literary Studies, and Art History (Area 10): 46.8% of CNR's outputs are in English, versus just 27.7% from other institutions. Likewise, in History, Philosophy and Pedagogy (Area 11a), the proportion of English-language outputs is 45.7% for CNR and 28.4% for other institutions.

In scientific and technical disciplines (Areas 1-9), English is dominant for both CNR and other institutions, with percentages nearing or reaching 100% across the board.

These figures indicate that in several disciplinary areas – particularly those where Italian tends to be more commonly used – CNR researchers exhibit a higher tendency to publish in English, underscoring a strategic orientation toward international dissemination and visibility.

By systematically investigating language practices within the organization, we can unveil the complex mechanisms through which scientific communication occurs and identify strategic opportunities for enhancing interdisciplinary dialogue. This approach not only addresses the practical challenges of multilingual scientific collaboration but also directly supports CNR's overarching mission of promoting inclusive, equitable, and globally integrated research practices.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data collection

The survey was conducted online among CNR researchers and technologists between June and August 2024, achieving a 13.3% response rate (n=910). This represents a strong outcome for an institutional survey, particularly considering it was conducted during the summer months. Response rates involving the research community usually range from 5% to 30%, positioning this survey well within the expected parameters.

The distribution across professional levels shows a sample of CNR's research community, from early-career researchers to senior directors. The survey was distributed in two stages via the institutional mailing list. The initial invitation was sent on June 27, 2024, reaching 6,833 recipients. A reminder was sent on July 24, 2024, to 6,852 recipients. The variation in recipient numbers reflects the ongoing updates to the institutional mailing list, which adjusts to staffing changes over time. As a result, at the time of the second contact, the list included more recipients than the first. This does not imply a change in the survey's outreach strategy, but rather a natural consequence of the list's dynamic nature. It is important to note that the second mailing functioned solely as a reminder not as a new invitation, sending the original mail text.

This systematic approach to data collection, utilizing the institutional mailing list as the primary distribution channel, helped ensure comprehensive coverage of the CNR research community.

3.2. Questionnaire design and structure

The questionnaire is structured into 6 sections and is developed to systematically explore the complex dynamics of language use in research practices across the CNR community, with particular attention to how researchers navigate between Italian and other languages in their professional activities.

Section 1: Introductory questions (Questions 1-8)

This section is designed to establish a demographic and professional profile of respondents. Beyond collecting basic information such as professional level, age group, and gender identity, it delves into crucial aspects of respondents' backgrounds, including their years of scientific activity and specific research fields. Notably, this section also addresses respondents' linguistic foundations by identifying their first language and proficiency levels in other languages, providing essential context for understanding their multilingual capabilities.

Section 2: Linguistic behaviours in research activities (Questions 9-9b)

This section focuses on linguistic practices in research, featuring a core question about language use in research activities. It includes conditional follow-up questions specifically targeting respondents who exclusively use Italian, exploring their motivations and perspectives on language demands in scientific settings. For these individuals (5 respondents), the questionnaire was considered concluded, and they were not directed to subsequent sections.

Section 3: The use of languages other than Italian in research activities (Questions 10-19)

This section focuses on the CNR research community who uses languages other than Italian (905 respondents), either exclusively or alongside Italian, and examines specific activities they perform as part of their scientific work.

It is specifically structured to examine how research staff navigates between Italian and other languages across different professional contexts. The questions progressively investigate language use patterns in various research activities, from writing and reading to teaching and outreach. A distinctive feature is the inclusion of questions about how language practices have been evolved throughout researchers' careers, providing insights into changing linguistic patterns in their work.

In this section, definitions to help users better understand the key activities related to research and scientific communication have been provided. These definitions clarify the scope and nature of various tasks involved in the scientific work. The activities' definitions are outlined as follows:

- *Text Writing*: Creation of scientific content such as books, book chapters, articles, reports, and any other written material that documents research findings and contributes to scientific discussion.
- *Oral Interaction*: Verbal communication during presentations, seminars, and meetings to share research results within the scientific community, collaborate with colleagues, and interact with funding bodies and stakeholders involved in research activities.
- *Reading*: Study and critical analysis of scientific works.
- *Teaching*: Dissemination of knowledge through formal education, including course design, lesson organization, and student tutoring.
- *Outreach* (oral or written): Sharing research findings in contexts outside the scientific world through various channels (popular publications, presentations, informational materials, etc.)⁴.

Section 4 Tools and services (Questions 20-22)

The section examines the research community's engagement with language tools and digital technologies, focusing on translation practices, automated translation tools, and the use of generative AI in multilingual research contexts. It explores how researchers leverage technological innovations to navigate linguistic challenges in scientific communication.

Section 5: English language usage (Questions 23-29)

The questions in this section are reserved for respondents who declared Italian as their native language (860 respondents). Given the predominance of English in international scientific communication, this section is dedicated to examining researchers' relationship with the English language. It explores motivations for English usage, challenges in English-language scholarly communication, and the impact of English-language requirements on publication and dissemination strategies.

⁴ Additionally, two questions are dedicated to the specific activities of *writing project proposals* to be submitted to funding organizations.

Section 6: Community perceptions on multilingualism and evaluation (Questions 30-33)

The final section is crafted to understand both the practical and perceptual aspects of multilingual research practices, while also exploring broader community attitudes toward multilingualism. It particularly focuses on understanding how language choices affect scientific freedom and research evaluation, incorporating questions about the impact of language on research assessment.

The questionnaire's design deliberately acknowledges Italian as the reference language for respondents while exploring their engagement with other languages, reflecting the position of CNR research community operating in both national and international contexts. Whenever the question requests the identification of languages, it provides the option to select from a list including all EU languages, along with an "Other" option for any additional languages. This approach allows for a nuanced understanding of how respondents balance local language requirements with global scientific communication needs. The organization of sections facilitates a natural progression from basic professional information to complex issues of language choice and its implications for research practice and evaluation.

3.3. Characteristics of the population investigated

The population targeted for this study encompasses individuals engaged in research within national and international contexts. The CNR research community works at various career stages, from early-career postdoctoral professionals contributing fresh perspectives, to senior scientists leading ground-breaking projects. The group under investigation includes researchers and technologists (entry-level position); senior researchers and senior technologists (intermediate-level positions); and research and technology directors (top-level position). Their roles are defined by their capacity to generate new knowledge, manage complex projects, and coordinate activities across diverse scientific and technological fields.

Researchers are professionals with demonstrated ability to contribute to advancements in their specific areas of expertise. Depending on their seniority, they can range from those working under supervision to individuals leading research projects and producing original, internationally recognized results. Their work involves scientific collaboration, publication in peer-reviewed journals, and participation in international research networks.

Technologists play a pivotal role in supporting research activities through their expertise in technological processes, project management, and technical innovation. They are responsible for designing and managing technological systems, often acting as the bridge between theoretical research and practical application. Their contributions are critical to the effective implementation of research projects and the development of new technologies.

4. Data analysis: Overview

In the analysis of this multilingual research practices survey, we employed a comprehensive methodological approach combining both quantitative and qualitative analytical methods. The quantitative analysis focused primarily on descriptive statistics to understand respondent profiles and professional distributions across the CNR research community. This was complemented by cross-tabulation analyses that revealed significant relationships between variables such as research disciplines, and language preferences in scientific activities.

Our qualitative analysis encompassed an interesting examination of open-ended responses, providing insights into the research community's experiences and attitudes toward multilingualism in their scientific work. In considering the methodological rigor of this study, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations that may influence the interpretation of our findings. While the 13.3% response rate (910 respondents from 6,833 researchers) is a solid outcome for this type of institutional survey and provides a substantial dataset for analysis, we must consider potential response biases in our sample. As with many self-reported studies, responses regarding language practices may reflect some degree of social desirability bias, particularly concerning proficiency levels and language use patterns.

Furthermore, the cross-sectional nature of the survey provides valuable insights into current multilingual practices at the CNR, though it necessarily captures a specific moment rather than evolutionary trends in language use and attitudes. This temporal limitation suggests opportunities for future longitudinal studies to track changes in multilingual practices over time.

The research was conducted with adherence to the CNR's ethical guidelines for research involving human participants⁵. We implemented measures to ensure participant anonymity throughout the data collection and analysis processes. Data handling and storage followed security protocols, protecting participant's personal data while maintaining data integrity. Participation was entirely voluntary.

⁵ Cf. CNR Research Ethics and Integrity Committee's Documents: <https://www.cnr.it/en/doc-ethics>

5. Results

The analysis includes responses to all 33 questionnaire items. For each question, the total number of respondents is reported alongside explanatory charts to facilitate data interpretation. It is important to note that certain questions were specifically directed at subsets of participants based on their responses to previous questions. Consequently, the number of respondents varies across questions and does not consistently equal 910 – the total number of participants who completed the full questionnaire. This methodological approach enables accurate representation of response patterns while maintaining fidelity to the survey's intended structure and participant pathways.

Section 1: Introductory questions

Q1: What is your professional profile?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 2 Question 1: Survey results

The majority of respondents (59.9%, $n=545$) hold researcher positions, forming the largest professional category. Senior researchers constitute the second-largest group (17%, $n=155$), followed by research directors (11.3%, $n=103$). The technological track shows a similar hierarchical distribution but with lower percentages: Technologists represent 8.7% ($n=79$) of respondents, while senior technologists and technology directors account for 2.4% ($n=22$) and 0.7% ($n=6$) respectively. This distribution reflects a traditional scientific career structure, with a broad base of researchers and a progressively narrowing representation at more senior levels, both in research and technological tracks. A comparison between the distribution of respondents and that of the invited participants is presented below (Table 2)⁶, offering insights into response behaviour across different profiles.

⁶ It is worth noting that some invited participants do not belong to any of the profiles listed in the table (e.g., Director, General Director, etc.). None of the individuals in these additional profiles responded to the questionnaire; therefore, the table refers to 6,677 invited participants.

Professional profile	Invited participants	Distribution of total invitees	Respondents	Distribution of total respondents	Response rate by profile
Research director	549	8.2%	103	11.3%	18.8%
Technology director	85	1.3%	6	0.7%	7.1%
Senior researcher	1268	19%	155	17%	12.2%
Senior technologist	215	3.2%	22	2.4%	10.2%
Researcher	3702	55.4%	545	59.9%	14.7%
Technologist	858	12.9%	79	8.7%	9.2%

Table 2 Invited participants and response rates by professional profile

Most invitees belong to the researcher profile (55.4%), followed by senior researchers at 19%, and technologists at 12.9%. This general distribution is largely reflected in the group of respondents, where researchers still represent the majority (59.9%). However, when analysing the response rate per profile (i.e., the percentage of contacts within each group who actually responded), some interesting differences emerge: Research directors showed the highest response rate at 18.8%, indicating a particularly engaged group; senior technologists and technologist directors also responded at relatively high rates (10.2% and 7.1%, respectively), despite representing a smaller share of the overall contacts; conversely, researchers, while being the largest group numerically, had a comparatively low response rate (14.7%), and technologists responded even less frequently (9.2%).

These findings suggest that higher-ranking or more senior profiles may be more responsive to surveys, potentially reflecting greater interest or a stronger sense of institutional responsibility.

Q2: What is your age? Please select your age range

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 3 Question 2: Survey results

The majority of respondents fall within the middle-age brackets, with 34.3% aged 40-49 years and 33.6% aged 50-59 years. The older age group (>60 years) represents 17.1% of respondents, while early-career researchers aged 31-39 constitute 13.8%. Notably, researchers under 30 years old form a very small proportion of the sample at just 1.1%. This age structure suggests a mature research community, with over two-thirds of respondents (67.9%) being between 40 and 59 years old, potentially reflecting both

career progression patterns and recruitment trends within the Italian research system (in 2023, the average age of CNR research and non-research staff was 51.5 years⁷).

Q3: To which gender identity do you identify?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 4 Question 3: Survey results

The gender distribution among respondents is notably balanced, with male participants constituting 49% and female participants comprising 48.1%, reflecting the gender distribution within the CNR (Table 3).

Gender	% of total CNR researchers and technologists	% of survey respondents
Female	49.3%	48.1%
Male	50.7%	49%

Table 3 Gender distribution of CNR researchers and technologists compared to survey respondents

A small percentage of respondents identified as non-binary (0.3%), while 2.5% chose not to disclose their gender identity. This distribution indicates a relatively equitable gender representation within the surveyed research population.

⁷https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/attivita/editoria/978888o8o6172_BILANCIO_DI_GENERE_CNR_2023_testo_def.pdf

Q4: How many years of research activity do you have?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 5 Question 4: Survey results

The majority have substantial research careers. The largest group consists of researchers with 10-20 years of experience (38.7%), followed closely by those with 21-30 years (33.5%). A significant portion of respondents (19.3%) report more than 30 years of research activity, indicating a considerable presence of highly experienced researchers. Early-career researchers with 1-9 years of experience represent a smaller fraction (8.5%) of the sample. This distribution suggests a well-established research community as respondents, with substantial accumulated expertise, as over 91% of respondents have more than 10 years of research experience.

Q5: What is your field of study?

[Respondents: 910 - two answers allowed]

Figure 6 Question 5: Survey results (representation across disciplines)

Figure 7 Question 5: Survey results (distribution of research fields among respondents)

The distribution of research fields among survey respondents shows a clear predominance of PE, representing 60% of the total selections. LS field constitutes the second largest field at 28.4%, while SH field accounts for 11.5% of the selections. The strong representation of PE, accounting for more than half of the selections, reflects the technical and applied science focus of the research community surveyed. Notably, respondents were allowed to select up to two research fields, meaning that the percentages reflect overall selections rather than exclusive classifications.

This distribution closely aligns with the results of an internal survey conducted by the CNR in 2025, which collected responses from 4,181 researchers (Table 4). In this survey, members of the scientific community were asked to identify one primary research field and up to two additional complementary fields of research activity. The consistency between the two datasets reinforces the validity of the current findings and further affirms the institution's disciplinary profile, which is predominantly centred on PE.

Research Field	Distribution of selections of fields of research in the survey	Distribution of selections of fields of research in 2025 CNR mapping campaign
Physical Sciences and Engineering	60%	58,2%
Life Sciences	28,4%	30,3%
Social Sciences and Humanities	11,5%	11,5%

Table 4 Research fields distribution in the survey and the 2025 CNR mapping campaign

When looking into the details, the breakdown of research fields highlights how specific sub-disciplines are distributed across the three main areas. Within Physical sciences and engineering, PE10 (Earth System Science) stands out as the most represented sub-discipline with 173 selections, followed by PE6 (Computer Science and Informatics) with 123. In Life sciences, LS8 (Environmental Biology, Ecology and Evolution) and

LS9 (Biotechnology and Biosystems Engineering) have the strongest presence, with 87 and 83 selections, respectively. On the other hand, the Social sciences and humanities category displays a more even distribution, with SH6 (the Study of the Human Past) leading at 31 selections.

This granular perspective reveals considerable variation in representation across sub-disciplines, with certain areas, especially in PE, showing significantly higher participation. The data suggests distinct research focuses and possibly institutional strengths in specific sub-disciplines. It is also worth noting that the total number of selections (1,291) surpasses the number of respondents (910), indicating that many respondents identified with multiple fields of study, including across different ERC sectors. Specifically, 80 respondents selected both a PE and an LS discipline, 43 selected both a PE and an SH discipline, and 6 selected both an LS and an SH discipline. This underscores the prevalence of interdisciplinary research activities.

Q6: What type(s) of research do you perform and what percentage of your time do you dedicate to each?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 8 Question 6: Survey results

The data highlights distinct patterns of research engagement across basic, applied, and experimental research types. For basic research, the distribution is relatively balanced: 37.9% of respondents dedicate 30-69% of their time, 33.1% spend 0-29%, and 29% invest 70-100% of their effort. In applied research, there is a strong concentration in the mid-range, with 55.1% of respondents dedicating 30-69% of their time, while 31% spend 0-29% and only 14% devote 70-100%. Experimental research shows a distinct distribution, with the majority (69.5%) spending minimal time (0-29%), 28.9% allocating 30-69%, and only 1.6% investing 70-100% of their effort.

These results indicate that most respondents adopt mixed approaches, with applied research showing the most balanced time distribution. In contrast, experimental research is often treated as a supplementary activity rather than a primary focus.

Q7: Is Italian your mother tongue?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 9 Question 7: Survey results

The overwhelming majority of respondents (95%) identify Italian as their mother tongue, while a small minority (5%) reported that it is not. This result highlights the linguistic homogeneity of the survey sample, suggesting that most participants share a common linguistic and cultural background. These findings can provide important context for interpreting subsequent survey questions, particularly those that may relate to language use and cultural perspectives (Section 5 and 6).

Q8: What languages other than your first language(s) do you know, and what is your level of proficiency?

[Respondents: 910 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 10 Question 8: Survey results (most common languages)

Figure 11 Question 8: Survey results (English language proficiency)

Among respondents, 99% reported knowledge of English, making it the most widely known second language. This is further reinforced by the breakdown of English proficiency levels: 58% are advanced users, 38% are independent users, and 3% are basic users, while only 1% reported having no knowledge of English. The high percentage of advanced and independent English users (96% combined) underscores the respondents' strong command of English, positioning it as a key tool for communication and research activities. In addition to English, other commonly known languages include French (52%), Spanish (33.3%), and German (15.4%), with significantly fewer respondents reporting knowledge of Portuguese (4.4%), Greek (3.1%), or Dutch (1.5%). These findings suggest that while a majority of respondents demonstrate multilingual capabilities, English proficiency stands out as the most dominant, likely reflecting its role as a global lingua franca.

Section 2: Linguistic behaviours in research activities

Q9: Do you use language(s) other than Italian across all aspects of your research activity?

[Respondents: 910]

Figure 12 Question 9: Survey results

The predominant response category “Yes, I use Italian and other languages” garnered 91.1% of responses. While this category might initially suggest widespread multilingualism, it should be noted that “other languages” in this context likely primarily refers to English, rather than indicating broader multilingual capabilities. A minority of respondents (8.4%) indicated using “only other languages,” while an even smaller fraction (0.5%) reported exclusive use of Italian. The extremely low percentage of Italian-only users suggests a population that is highly integrated with at least one other language, presumably English, given its status as a global lingua franca.

The data may reflect a binary linguistic environment rather than true multilingualism, as the questionnaire design does not differentiate between bilingualism (Italian-English) and broader multilingual capabilities.

Q9a. Why don't you use languages other than Italian?

- Because in my field, Italian is a language used by the international research community.
- Because I do not feel confident in other languages.
- Because it is not necessary for my career.
- Because I do not participate in activities that specifically require the use of languages other than Italian.
- Because I am specifically interested in sharing my research findings with Italian researchers, the general public, and/or policymakers in Italy.
- Because Italian is my native language, and I believe that giving up one's language is a cultural regression.
- Because my research is focused on Italy and is primarily of interest to Italian speakers.

[Respondents: 5 - multiple answers allowed]

There are different reasons why respondents choose not to use languages other than Italian. One reason, cited by three respondents, is that their activities do not specifically require the use of other languages. Additionally, two respondents indicated a lack of confidence in using languages other than Italian. Some respondents also pointed to a focus on sharing their work with Italian audiences, including fellow researchers, the general public, and policymakers in Italy, as well as the specific relevance of their research to Italian speakers – both reasons were each cited by one respondent. Notably, none of the participants felt that using Italian was necessary because it is an international research language, nor did they mention that their career goals made the use of other languages unnecessary. Similarly, no one attributed their choice solely to a belief in preserving the use of Italian as a cultural stance. This suggests that practical considerations, such as the relevance of their work to local contexts and a lack of necessity for other languages in their current roles, primarily drive this decision.

Q9b: It is a common perception that in various contexts (e.g., teaching, funding procedures, assessment exercises), there is an increasing demand for the use of the English language in Italy: express your level of agreement with the following statements:

- (1) An increasing demand for the use of the English language in a globalized world is inevitable and corresponds to a real need
- (2) An increasing demand for the use of the English language does not seem to be justified by valid reasons
- (3) I consider an increasing demand for the use of the English language to be harmful to Italian culture and science

[Respondents: 5]

Some of the respondents acknowledged the inevitability and necessity of this trend in a globalized world. Specifically, two participants strongly agreed⁸ and one agreed with the statement that an increasing demand is inevitable (statement 1), while two remained neutral. No respondents expressed disagreement, suggesting broad acceptance of the practical importance of English in an interconnected academic environment.

In contrast, when asked whether this demand is unjustified (statement 2), the majority of participants disagreed. Two expressed disagreement and one strongly disagreed, while two were neutral. Notably, no one agreed with this statement, indicating that the perceived justification for using English is widely recognized among respondents.

When considering the potential cultural implications of this trend (statement 3), opinions were less polarized. Three respondents adopted a neutral stance, while two strongly disagreed. No participants viewed the growing emphasis on English as harmful, suggesting that concerns about cultural or scientific erosion are not prevalent within this group. Overall, the data reflects a pragmatic outlook among these few respondents, who generally view the use of English as an essential and justified component of global scientific and professional engagement. Concerns about negative cultural impacts or the lack of valid reasons for this trend appear minimal, highlighting a broader acceptance of English as a key tool in contemporary research and collaboration.

⁸ Respondents were given the opportunity to choose from five response options: Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly disagree.

Section 3: The use of languages other than Italian in research activities

Q10: Which language other than Italian do you primarily use in all aspects of your research work?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 13 Question 10: Survey results

English stands out as the most widely used foreign language among participants in their research activities, with 890 respondents reporting its use. Other languages, such as French (5), Spanish (3), Czech (1), and a small category of “Other languages” (6), were mentioned by far fewer participants. Among these “Other languages” were Arabic (1), Persian (1), Italian Sign Language (2), and Russian (2). These findings emphasize the dominant role of English as the lingua franca in scientific research. The frequent use of English confirms its prominent role in international research contexts, suggesting that a good command of the language may often be important for participating in global academic exchanges.

Q11: Which language(s) have you used in your text writing activities over the past five years, and what percentage of use does each language represent?

[Respondents: 905 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 14 Question 11: Survey results

Q11a: How has the use of languages other than Italian changed in your text writing activities throughout your career?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 15 Question 11a: Survey results

Questions 11 and 11a quantify the distribution of language use in scientific writing, providing concrete data about multilingual practices in research publication and documentation. They also examine how respondents' language choices in scientific writing have changed throughout their careers, particularly their shift between Italian and other languages. English is undeniably the dominant language (894 users), followed by Italian (627 users), and then, to a significantly lesser extent, by French (41 users), Spanish (21 users), German (7 users), and various other languages each selected only once.

While a significant portion of respondents (67.3%) have consistently used the same languages throughout their careers, a notable number have increased their use of languages other than Italian over time (24.1%). This shift likely reflects the growing demand for international communication in academia. However, a small group (2.9%) has decreased their use of non-Italian languages, possibly due to changes in their research focus or institutional requirements. A portion of respondents found it difficult to pinpoint specific changes in their language use over time. Further research could delve into the factors influencing these trends, such as institutional policies, disciplinary differences, and the impact of international collaborations.

Q12: Which language(s) have you used in your oral interaction activities over the past five years, and what percentage of use does each language represent?

[Respondents: 905 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 16 Question 12: Survey results

Q12a: How has the use of languages other than Italian changed in your oral interaction activities throughout your career?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 17 Question 12a: Survey results

Questions 12 and 12a examine oral communication patterns in research and investigate how respondents' language choices in oral communication have changed throughout their careers, particularly their shift between Italian and other languages.

The data demonstrates a clear dominance of English (895 users) and Italian (799 users) in oral research interactions, underscoring their roles as primary languages of communication within the research community. Other European languages, such as French (81 users) and Spanish (60 users), show significantly lower usage, with German

(13 users) and several others (Portuguese, Greek, Lithuanian, Czech, Irish, and Dutch) having minimal usage, each with fewer than 10 users.

The majority of respondents (60.6%) consistently used the same language(s) throughout their career. A significant portion (21.8%) has shifted to preferring other languages than Italian over time. Meanwhile, 9.2% used other languages than Italian more in the past but reduced their usage, and 8.5% cannot clearly describe their changes in language use. These results suggest stability in language preferences for most, with a smaller group demonstrating dynamic shifts.

Q13: Which languages have you used in your reading activity over the last five years and in what percentage have you used each language?

[Respondents: 905 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 18 Question 13: Survey results

Q13a: How has the use of languages other than Italian changed in your reading activities throughout your career?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 19 Question 13a: Survey results

Questions 13 and 13a assess respondents' consumption of scientific literature across languages and examine how the research community's language choices in reading activity have changed throughout their careers, particularly their shift between Italian

and other languages. The data on reading activities highlights the dominance of English, used by 901 of 905 respondents, reflecting its status as the primary language for accessing global scientific literature. Italian, cited by 578 respondents, remains significant. Other languages, such as French (83 respondents) and Spanish (43 respondents), show moderate use, while German and additional languages are mentioned less frequently, likely in niche contexts.

Regarding language use evolution, 71.4% reported consistent use of the same languages, primarily English and Italian. Meanwhile, 21.5% noted an increasing preference for languages other than Italian, reflecting a shift toward multilingualism, while 2.3% reported decreased use of non-Italian languages. A small portion (4.8%) found it difficult to describe changes in their language use.

Q14: Have you engaged in teaching activities in the last five years?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 20 Question 14: Survey results

Q14a: Which language(s) have you used in your teaching activities over the past five years, and what percentage of use does each language represent?

[Respondents: 593 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 21 Question 14a: Survey results

Q14b: How has the use of languages other than Italian changed in your teaching activities throughout your career?

[Total Respondents: 905 - Respondents with teaching experience: 775]

Figure 22 Question 14b: Survey results

It is worth noting, first and foremost, that the CNR's scientific community is primarily focused on research, rather than teaching, as research activities are its core mission. Consequently, CNR research staff does not have a formal teaching obligation, which distinguishes them from academic staff in other institutions. This context is crucial for interpreting the responses to Questions 14, 14a, and 14b on teaching activities and the use of languages in academic education.

A majority of respondents, 66%, indicated that they had engaged in teaching activities in the past five years, showcasing the active educational role of most participants. However, 34% reported not engaging in teaching, highlighting that a significant proportion of the CNR research community may focus more on research.

Among those who reported their teaching activities (593 respondents), Italian emerged as the most commonly used language, with 527 respondents citing it, reflecting its role as the primary medium of instruction for most academic courses in Italy. English was the second most frequently used language, reported by 396 respondents. This reflects the predominant role of Italian as the primary language in Italian academic settings. However, the significant use of English is also noteworthy. In the Italian higher education context, where there has been ongoing discussion about the need to ensure that all students have the opportunity to study in their native language, the relevance of English-language indicates a notable shift. It underscores the increasing trend towards internationalization in academia and the growing demand for courses conducted in English to accommodate a diverse, often global, student audience. Other languages, such as French (22 respondents) and Spanish (16 respondents), were reported at much lower levels, likely reflecting specific courses, departments, or collaborations with speakers of those languages. The minimal use of languages like German, Portuguese, Lithuanian, Czech, and Greek suggests their role is limited to niche contexts or specific academic fields where these languages are relevant.

In addition to language usage, the evolution of teaching practices over time offers some insights. The assessment is based on responses of 775 respondents, with a notable

exclusion of 130 respondents who reported no teaching experience. A majority of respondents, 65.4%, reported consistently using the same language(s) throughout their careers, indicating a stable approach to language choice in teaching, likely dominated by Italian. However, 15.5% indicated a shift toward a preference for using languages other than Italian, suggesting a growing trend to incorporate English or other languages in response to the demands of internationalization. Conversely, 5.4% stated that they used languages other than Italian more frequently in the past, but this usage has since decreased, which could be due to institutional policies or a return to a localized teaching focus. 13.7% of respondents expressed difficulty in describing how their use of languages other than Italian has changed, reflecting the fluidity or complexity of their teaching experiences.

Q15: Which language(s) do you use when engaging in outreach activities (oral presentation)?

[Respondents: 905 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 23 Question 15: Survey results

Italian is the primary language used for oral presentations in outreach activities, followed by English. While Italian remains dominant, the presence of other languages, albeit to a lesser extent, suggests a diverse range of outreach activities and a desire to engage with a broader, more international audience. The prevalence of Italian likely reflects the importance of reaching local audiences and communicating research findings to the general public in Italy. Conversely, the significant use of English indicates a growing trend towards international outreach and collaborations. The presence of other languages further highlights the diversity of outreach activities and the potential for engaging with specific linguistic communities.

Q16: Which language(s) do you use when engaging in outreach activities (written text production)?

[Respondents: 905 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 24 Question 16: Survey results

English is the most frequently used language for written text production in outreach activities, with 749 respondents indicating its use. Italian follows closely with 678 respondents, highlighting the importance of both national and international communication in written outreach efforts. A smaller number of respondents reported using the following languages: French (19), Spanish (13), German (3), Dutch (2), Czech (1), Greek (1), Polish (1), Portuguese (1) Other languages (3).

While Italian is predominantly used for oral outreach activities due to its connection with local communities, English plays a crucial role in written communication, enabling the research community to connect with global audiences and foster international collaborations. The preference for English in written outreach may also stem from the availability of existing materials, such as research publications, reports, or outreach resources, which are often already produced in English. Research communities may leverage these pre-existing resources, as they provide a ready-to-use foundation for communication with international audiences. This practical consideration likely contributes to the increased use of English in written forms of outreach, while Italian remains the preferred language for direct, localized oral interactions.

Q17: How difficult is it for you to communicate research results produced in languages other than Italian to non-scientific audiences in Italian?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 25 Question 17: Survey results

A significant majority of respondents (54.1%) experience no difficulty in communicating research results produced in foreign languages to non-scientific audiences in Italian. This suggests a strong level of language proficiency and adaptability among respondents. While a substantial portion (23.1%) perceives some level of difficulty, only a small percentage (13.3%) reports moderate difficulties. Interestingly, a minority, though not negligible, of respondents (5.1% and 4.4%, respectively) experiences significant or even great difficulties in translating and communicating research findings across languages. To provide a characterization of this group, it can be noted that 8% report that Italian is not their native language. According to the disciplinary research fields chosen by the respondents (Q5), there is the following distribution of selected fields across various areas⁹: 17% SH, 33% LS, and 60% PE.

Q18: Do you participate in funding application procedures when the use of a language other than Italian is required?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 26 Question 18: Survey results

⁹ As previously mentioned, it is important to note that respondents could select up to two fields from more than one broader area.

The data shows that a high percentage of respondents (92.6%) participate in funding application procedures even when the use of a language other than Italian is required. This indicates a strong willingness to engage in international research funding opportunities. A small proportion (5.3%) participate, but request support from their institution, suggesting a need for institutional support in navigating language-related challenges in funding applications. Only 2.1% of respondents do not participate in such funding procedures, likely due to various factors such as language barriers or lack of interest in international funding opportunities.

Q19: Do you feel disadvantaged if you are required to use a language other than Italian to participate in funding application procedures?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 27 Question 19: Survey results

Nearly a quarter of respondents (23%) report feeling disadvantaged when required to use a language other than Italian in funding applications. While this may appear to be a minority, it is a meaningful proportion that sheds light on the challenges some respondents face in navigating language requirements in international competitions.

For these individuals, the language barrier may stem from a lack of confidence, gaps in proficiency, or even the added stress of competing with native or highly fluent speakers. This disadvantage could also reflect differences in access to institutional resources, such as language training or translation services, which could make a significant difference in leveling the playing field.

At the same time, the fact that 77% of respondents do not feel disadvantaged suggests a broader resilience within the research community. It may reflect a high degree of adaptability and preparedness among respondents, who are increasingly accustomed to operating in a multilingual scientific environment.

However, as previously mentioned the 23% figure is not insignificant. It serves as a reminder that language requirements, while navigable for most, still create barriers for a notable subset of respondents. Addressing these challenges by expanding access to language training, improving translation services, or offering tailored support could help ensure that all scientists have an equal chance to engage in global funding competitions.

Section 4: Tools and services

Q20: Have you published texts that were translated into a language different from the original?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 28 Question 20: Survey results

Only 14% of respondents have published texts that were translated into a language different from the original, while the majority (86%) have not. This indicates that translating research texts is not a widespread practice among respondents, possibly reflecting a reliance on dominant languages (presumably English or Italian) for original publications, minimizing the need for translation.

Q20a: If your publications have been translated, specify into which language(s)

[Respondents: 123 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 29 Question 20a: Survey results

English is the most frequently mentioned language (63 users), indicating its role as the dominant language for disseminating translated research. Other EU languages such as Italian (24 users), Spanish (22 users), French (21 users), and German (13 users) also

hold significance, though with much lower representation. A variety of additional languages, including Portuguese, Slovenian, and others, are represented in smaller numbers, with many having fewer than five users. Under the option “Other” various languages are included such as Chinese (10 users) and Russian (8 users). This pattern reflects the centrality of English in international research communication, with regional languages serving more localized roles in translation efforts.

Q20b: What are the main reasons that led to the translation of your texts?

- Personal initiative
- Request from colleagues
- Request by journals or editors of collective works
- Request by publishers
- Request by funders
- Other

[Respondents: 123 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 30 Question 20b: Survey results

The primary reasons for translating texts are driven predominantly by external factors, with requests from publishers (55 responses) and journals or editors of collective works (50 responses) standing out as the most frequent motivators. Requests from colleagues and funders also contribute but to a lesser extent. Personal initiative accounts for only 18 responses, indicating that respondents rarely undertake translation without external prompts. The data highlights how translation efforts are shaped more by institutional or professional demands than by individual decision-making.

Q21: Do you use automated translation tools (e.g., Google Translate, DeepL) in your research activities?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 31 Question 21: Survey results

The majority of respondents (54.9%) use automated translation tools to some extent in their research activities, while 22.9% use them regularly. A smaller proportion, 11%, avoid these tools due to concerns about reliability, and 11.2% state they do not use and will not use such tools in the future. This suggests that automated translation tools are widely adopted, though concerns about accuracy and reliability persist for a minority of respondents.

Q21a: If you use automated translation tools, how often do you use them when reading?

Q21b: If you use automated translation tools, how often do you use them when writing?

[Total Respondents: 905 - Respondents using automated translation tools: 704]

Figure 32 Question 21a-21b: Survey result

The data indicates distinct patterns in the use of automated translation tools for reading and writing tasks. Interestingly, 22.2% of all survey respondents *never* use them.

When it comes to reading, these tools are used relatively infrequently: 44.4% of respondents report using them *rarely*, and only 9% use them *often*. An additional 24.4% indicate occasional use (*sometimes*). This suggests that many feel confident in their reading comprehension of other languages and prefer to rely on their own language skills when interpreting written material.

In contrast, writing tasks see a more active use of such tools. While 11.4% of respondents report *rare* use, a significantly larger portion (44.0%) report using them *sometimes*, and 22.4% use them *often*. These findings point to a greater reliance on automated tools in writing, possibly due to the higher demands for linguistic precision and fluency when producing content in another language.

Q22: Do you use generative artificial intelligence tools (e.g., ChatGPT) to produce texts in various languages?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 33 Question 22: Survey result

A significant portion of respondents (52.3%) have never experimented with generative AI tools for text production. This suggests that the adoption of these tools within the research community is still in its early stages. A considerable number of respondents (42.4%) have experimented with these tools but do not use them regularly. This indicates that respondents are exploring the potential of AI-powered language models but have not yet fully integrated them into their workflow. Only a small percentage of respondents (5.3%) regularly use these tools to produce texts in various languages. This may suggest that, despite growing awareness and experimentation, the widespread and consistent use of AI for text generation in research remains limited. The relatively low percentage of regular users may reflect both cautious adoption and the need for further developments before these tools become an integral part of research workflows.

Section 5: English language usage¹⁰

Q23: When you use the English language, why do you do so?

- It is the lingua franca of my research field
- It ensures international visibility
- It is necessary to collaborate with foreign researchers
- I am more familiar with English terminology
- Journals I am interested in accept manuscripts only in English
- It is necessary to obtain funding or a research position
- I assume English papers are better evaluated
- I never use English

[Respondents: 860 - multiple answers allowed]

Figure 34 Question 23: Survey result

The most cited reasons were that English is the lingua franca of the respondents research field (683 responses) and necessary for collaboration with foreign researchers (680 responses), closely followed by the requirement of publishing in English-only journals (619 responses). These three reasons underscore the structural and institutional pressures driving English use. Other common reasons included ensuring international visibility (525 responses) and the necessity to obtain funding or a research position (339 responses). While less cited than other reasons, this highlights that English functions not only as a communicative tool but also as a strategic requirement for accessing academic resources and career opportunities on an international scale.

Interestingly, only 214 responses indicated a personal familiarity with English terminology as a reason, suggesting that the use of English is less about individual linguistic preference and more about systemic academic norms. Moreover, the minimal number of responses indicating that English is never used or that its use is based on assumptions of better evaluation of English papers (62 responses) further underscores that English functions less as a choice and more as a necessity in the global research ecosystem.

¹⁰ As stated above, the questions in this section were reserved for respondents who declared Italian as their native language (860 respondents).

Q24: How would you describe the distribution of your peer-reviewed manuscripts throughout your career, distinguishing between those in English and those in languages other than English?

[Respondents: 860]

Figure 35 Question 24: Survey result

The distribution of peer-reviewed manuscripts overwhelmingly highlights English as the dominant language for scientific publication. With 91.2% of respondents reporting that 80-100% of their manuscripts are written in English, it is evident that publishing in English is now the standard for the vast majority of respondents (this percentage includes the 67.5% of respondents who publish exclusively in English). The 6.7% of respondents who reported publishing 40-79% of their manuscripts in English represent a smaller group. This suggests a balance between local or regional publishing traditions and the broader push toward English-language publications. Respondents in this group may work in disciplines or contexts where non-English languages retain some significance, or they may be at earlier stages of adopting English as the primary medium for their scientific output. Only 2.1% of respondents indicated that 0-39% of their manuscripts are in English. This minority likely reflects individuals who are highly specialized in national or regional studies, those working in disciplines where local language publication is still common, or those who face significant barriers to publishing in English, such as limited proficiency or lack of institutional support.

Q25: How would you describe the distribution of your participation in conferences in your specific research field throughout your career, distinguishing between those in English and those in languages other than English?

[Respondents: 860]

Figure 36 Question 25: Survey result

The distribution of participation in conferences in the specific research field throughout one's career, distinguishing between English and other languages, reveals interesting patterns. A small proportion, 4.2%, reported attending 0-39% of their conferences in English. Meanwhile, 21.4% indicated that 40-79% of their conferences were in English. The majority, 74.4%, stated that 80-100% of their conference participation occurred in English; this percentage includes the 26.5% of respondents who have participated exclusively at conferences held in English. This highlights the central role of English in facilitating academic exchange, reinforcing its status as the lingua franca of global scientific communication. However, it is important to note that this dominance may also be influenced by the higher availability of conferences held in English, which could skew the data. The greater number of English-language conferences offers more opportunities for participation, potentially leading to a higher reported attendance in English, regardless of respondents' personal language preferences.

Q26: How frequently have you avoided participating in a conference in English (either to present your research or simply to attend) due to a lack of confidence in communicating in English?

[Respondents: 860]

Figure 37 Question 26: Survey result

The data highlights the central role of English in scientific conferences, with 74.3% of respondents *never* avoiding participation due to language barriers. However, about 25.7% have at least occasionally refrained, with 5.5% doing so *often*. This suggests that while most respondents feel equipped to engage in English, a notable minority perceives the language as a barrier, potentially limiting their scientific visibility and opportunities. Addressing this through targeted language training or mentoring could enhance inclusivity and equity in global research participation.

Q27: What is your stance on the language policy of journals that publish exclusively in English?

- The journal takes precedence over the requirement of using exclusively English
- I only publish in journals that accept contributions in multiple languages
- I never consider the request to use English a problem
- Other

[Respondents: 860]

Figure 38 Question 27: Survey result

A significant majority, 78.6%, state that they never consider the requirement to use English a problem. This suggests that most respondents are comfortable with English as the standard language of scholarly communication.

Interestingly, 18.5% of respondents indicated that they do not let the journal's language policy influence their decision, as they consider it more important to publish in their preferred journal than to be required to use English exclusively. However, a very small percentage, 0.7%, report that they only publish in journals accepting contributions in multiple languages, highlighting a niche preference for multilingual inclusivity. Additionally, 2.2% chose "Other", which might reflect nuanced or alternative perspectives on the issue.

The accompanying open-ended free text comments revealed interesting insights into individuals' attitudes towards scientific communication. Respondents articulated nuanced perspectives, ranging from concerns about linguistic and conceptual impoverishment to pragmatic acceptance of English as a global research language. Some provocative suggestions emerged, such as using AI for comprehensive translation to preserve multilingual inclusivity, highlighting the ongoing tension between linguistic standardization and cultural diversity in academic/scientific discourse. One respondent acknowledges the linguistic reductionism of English-only policies while pragmatically continuing to publish in English. Another comment captures the nuanced perspective of English as a necessary global lingua franca, while simultaneously advocating for true multilingualism that extends beyond Western linguistic boundaries.

Q28: Have you ever had a manuscript rejected by an English-language journal due to insufficient language quality?

[Respondents: 860]

Figure 39 Question 28: Survey result

The vast majority, 87%, have never had a manuscript rejected due to language quality, suggesting that most respondents are either confident in their English writing skills or utilize resources like professional editing services to ensure quality. However, 13% of respondents have experienced rejections due to language, which, while a minority, represents a quite relevant challenge for a portion of the scientific community. This finding highlights the continued need for support mechanisms, such as language training, editorial assistance, or institutional resources, to help the research community overcome linguistic barriers and enhance equitable access to publication opportunities in English-language journals.

Q29: What percentage of your English-language publications have you paid for a professional service to improve the language quality?
 [Respondents: 860]

Figure 40 Question 29: Survey result

Figure 41 Question 29: Survey result (percentage of manuscripts revised)

A majority, 63%, have never paid for professional service to improve the language quality. This suggests that many respondents, as already highlighted in previous responses, either rely on their own language proficiency, institutional support, or informal peer review to meet language quality standards. On the other hand, 37% have paid for professional language services, indicating a substantial portion of respondents recognize the need for external help to ensure their manuscripts meet the required linguistic standards. Among those, most (27.8%) have only a small fraction (1-25%) of their manuscripts revised. Very few researchers utilize these services extensively: only 3.8% have 26-50% of their manuscripts revised, 1.5% have 51-75% revised, and 3.1% have 76-100% revised. This indicates that while approximately one-third of researchers do seek some professional revision assistance, they typically limit this to a minor portion of their manuscripts. This underscores the perceived importance of high-quality language in academic publishing and raises concerns about accessibility, as the cost of professional services may create disparities in publication opportunities, particularly for individuals whose research is not funded by projects.

Section 6: Community perceptions on multilingualism and evaluation

Q30: What is your opinion regarding the following statements about language choice and evaluation practices?

- (1) In recruitment/promotion procedures in Italy, certain languages may be preferred.
- (2) In project funding procedures in Italy, certain languages may be preferred.
- (3) In the national evaluation exercise (VQR), certain languages may be preferred
- (4) In recruitment and project funding procedures abroad, certain languages may be preferred.
- (5) Academic conventions require the use of certain languages to effectively communicate research findings.
- (6) Maximising the impact and accessibility of research globally requires the use of certain languages.

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 42 Question 30: Survey result (first statement)

Q.30 (2) In project funding procedures in Italy, certain languages may be preferred

Figure 43 Question 30: Survey result (second statement)

Q.30 (3) In the national evaluation exercise (VQR), certain languages may be preferred

Figure 44 Question 30: Survey result (third statement)

Q.30 (4) In recruitment and project funding procedures abroad, certain languages may be preferred

Figure 45 Question 30: Survey result (fourth statement)

Q.30 (5) Academic conventions require the use of certain languages to effectively communicate research findings

Figure 46 Question 30: Survey result (fifth statement)

Figure 47 Question 30: Survey result (sixth statement)

The responses to the questions about language preferences in recruitment, promotion, project funding indicate a clear distinction between national and international contexts. Regarding recruitment and promotion procedures in Italy (statement 1), 44% of respondents believe that certain languages may be preferred, which suggests a general perception that language plays a role in these processes. However, the significant proportion of neutral responses (33%) and those who disagreed (23%) indicate that this preference may not be a universally acknowledged or dominant factor in Italy, leaving room for uncertainty or variation in individual experiences. Similarly, when it comes to project funding procedures (statement 2) in Italy, 44% again agree that language preference exists, while 34% are neutral. This points to a general belief that language plays a role, but, like in recruitment and promotion, it is not seen as an absolute determinant for everyone. In the case of the national evaluation exercise (statement 3) there is a similar agreement (40%), yet the responses remain somewhat divided, with a significant proportion (35%) remaining neutral. This suggests again that while language may influence evaluations, the overall effect is not universally acknowledged by all respondents.

On the other hand, when the focus shifts to international contexts, the perceptions change dramatically. A large majority, 73%, agree that language preferences are much stronger abroad, particularly in recruitment and project funding procedures (statement 4). Only a small percentage (9%) disagreed. This disparity between national and international contexts reinforces the idea that while language may not always be a deciding factor in Italy, it certainly becomes a more prominent consideration globally.

Regarding academic conventions (statement 5), a clear majority of respondents (79%) agree that using specific languages is essential to communicate research effectively. This aligns with the broader global trends in academic publishing and conferences, where English is the dominant language.

The perception that using a specific language across the research community (statement 6) maximizes the impact and accessibility of research globally is even more strongly supported, with 89% in agreement. This overwhelming consensus highlights the reality that, for the research community seeking global visibility, proficiency in and use of a language other than their mother tongue, most commonly English, is considered essential.

Q31: Have you ever received negative feedback from a review panel for not including publications in languages other than Italian in one of your applications?

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 48 Question 31: Survey result

The vast majority, 98%, have not received negative feedback from a review panel for excluding publications in languages other than Italian. This suggests that the language of publication (beyond Italian) has not been a significant issue in review panels or applications. However, a small minority, 2%, have experienced negative feedback for this reason, indicating that in some cases, there may be an expectation for respondents to demonstrate a broader linguistic scope in their publications.

Q32: What is your opinion regarding the following statements about the use of a language other than one's own and its relationship to academic freedom?

- (1) The obligation to use a language other than one's own could potentially limit the ability to express complex ideas effectively.
- (2) I recognize that using languages other than my own can present challenges, but I see it as an intellectual growth and global collaboration opportunity, rather than a threat to academic freedom.
- (3) I believe that academic freedom extends to the choice of language and should allow the use of one's own language in the pursuit of knowledge and scientific exchange.

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 49 Question 32: Survey result (first statement)

Figure 50 Question 32: Survey result (second statement)

Figure 51 Question 32: Survey result (third statement)

The first statement, which suggests that the obligation to use a language other than one's own could limit the ability to express complex ideas effectively, garnered agreement from 50% of respondents (15% fully agree, 35% agree). This indicates that a significant portion of respondents perceive linguistic limitations as a potential barrier to fully conveying nuanced or intricate scientific concepts. However, 32% disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting that many do not see this as a serious limitation, while 19% remained neutral, reflecting mixed opinions on this point.

The second statement, which frames using other languages as an opportunity for intellectual growth and global collaboration rather than a threat to academic freedom, was met with overwhelming agreement. A total of 85% of respondents (39% fully agree, 46% agree) endorsed this perspective, showing a strong recognition of the value of multilingualism in fostering global academic networks and personal development. Only 4% disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating minimal resistance to this idea.

The third statement, which ties academic freedom to the choice of language and the ability to use one's native language in scientific exchange, elicited more varied responses. While 32% (10% fully agree, 22% agree) supported this view, 38% (27% disagree, 11% strongly disagree) opposed it, highlighting that academic freedom is not necessarily tied to language choice and does not inherently require the right to use one's native language in scientific discourse and knowledge exchange. Additionally, 30% remained neutral, signaling a lack of consensus or strong feelings on this matter.

Q33. What is your opinion regarding the following statements?

- (1) While the prevalence of English-language publications in citation databases is advantageous for the global dissemination of research, it can marginalize non-English-speaking researchers and their contributions.
- (2) The prevalence of English-language publications in citation databases underscores the need for greater efforts to promote multilingualism and inclusivity in academic communication.
- (3) Citation databases that mainly feature English-language publications can perpetuate linguistic biases and hinder the visibility of important research conducted in languages other than English.
- (4) English-language publications in citation databases represent international excellence and allow for the measurement of global scientific impact.

[Respondents: 905]

Figure 52 Question 33: Survey result (first statement)

Figure 53 Question 33: Survey result (second statement)

Figure 54 Question 33: Survey result (third statement)

Figure 55 Question 33: Survey result (fourth statement)

The first statement, which highlights the potential marginalization of non-English-speaking researchers due to the prominence of English-language publications, elicited agreement from 45% of respondents (11% fully agree, 34% agree), indicating a significant concern about inclusivity in scientific communication. However, 45% disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting that many do not perceive this as a pressing issue. The remaining 21% were neutral, reflecting a balance of opinions within the scientific community. These neutral responses may indicate that, for some respondents, the issue of language dominance in scientific publishing does not strongly affect their own experience or research practices, or they may be unsure about its broader implications.

In response to the second statement, which emphasizes the need to promote multilingualism and inclusivity in scientific communication, a majority of 52% (16% fully agree, 36% agree) supported this idea, while 23% disagreed or strongly disagreed, and 25% were neutral. This suggests a broad recognition of the value of linguistic diversity, even if it is not universally prioritized.

The third statement, which argues that citation databases focusing on English-language publications perpetuate linguistic biases and reduce the visibility of research in other languages, received agreement from 38% (10% fully agree, 28% agree), with a comparable 36% in disagreement and 27% neutral. This split opinion reflects the tension between recognizing the global standardization benefits of English and the desire to protect and promote linguistic diversity.

Finally, the statement asserting that English-language publications represent international excellence and enable the measurement of global scientific impact garnered agreement from 47% (14% fully agree, 33% agree). However, 21% disagreed or strongly disagreed, and 33% were neutral. This indicates that while many respondents value the global impact of English-language publications, a substantial proportion remain either skeptical or indifferent to this characterization.

Overall, the data suggests a widespread acknowledgment of both the benefits and limitations of the dominance of English in citation databases. While many recognize the role of English as a standard for international communication, there is also considerable support for efforts to address linguistic biases and foster greater inclusivity and visibility for research in other languages. The divided opinions highlight the ongoing debate about balancing global impact with the preservation of linguistic diversity in academic communication.

6. Survey data cross-analysis: Key insights into multilingualism in scientific activities

Building on the comprehensive survey analysis previously described, this section explores key cross-analyses of survey responses, shedding light on specific trends in multilingual scientific practices, with a particular focus on SH.

6.1. Language(s) use across scientific activities

Figure 56 Consistency in language use across scientific activities

An examination of language use patterns reveals varying degrees of consistency across scientific activities. Reading demonstrates the highest stability, with 71.4% of respondents maintaining consistent language choices in this domain. Writing follows with 67.3% of respondents showing stable language use patterns, while teaching activities maintain a moderately high consistency rate of 65.4%. Oral interaction exhibits the greatest variability, with 60.6% of respondents maintaining consistent language use.

These patterns reveal a gradient of linguistic stability across scientific practices, where receptive activities show the highest consistency in language use, while interactive communication demonstrates greater variability. This distribution suggests that the nature of the scientific activity influences the degree of language consistency, with oral interaction potentially requiring more linguistic flexibility compared to other scientific functions.

Figure 57 Reported shift to non-Italian languages across scientific activities over time

With reference to the evolution of the use of languages other than Italian throughout one’s career and across different activities, writing activities show the highest rate of language transition at 24.1%, representing the most significant shift toward non-Italian languages. Oral interaction and reading demonstrate comparable transition rates of 21.8% and 21.5% respectively, indicating a substantial evolution in both productive and receptive language skills. Teaching activities exhibit the lowest transition rate at 15.5%, suggesting greater persistence of Italian language use in higher education context.

6.2 Language usage patterns in SH

Figure 58 Transition to non-Italian languages across scientific activities

Analysis of survey data regarding language usage patterns in SH research reveals complex multilingual dynamics within the scientific community.

The majority of respondents in both SH and all disciplines employ a multilingual approach, with 92.7% of SH researchers and 91.1% of all researchers using both Italian and other languages. This suggests a quite relevant internationalization of research outputs, particularly in SH fields.

A small percentage of respondents use only Italian, with 3.2% in SH and 0.5% across all disciplines. This indicates that Italian as the sole language of research is more prevalent in SH, but remains marginal overall. This finding may reflect the national relevance of specific research topics or a preference for local academic engagement in SH fields.

Conversely, the use of only non-Italian languages is slightly more common in all disciplines (8.4%) than in SH (4%). This difference may be attributed to the dominance of English as a lingua franca in LS and PE fields, where international collaboration and publication in English are more pronounced.

Figure 59 Changes in language use in writing activities: SH vs. All Disciplines

Longitudinal analysis of language usage patterns reveals significant temporal dynamics in writing activities. Within the SH domain, 31.7% of respondents reported an increasing preference for languages other than Italian throughout their careers. This trend appears to be driven by external factors, particularly the pressure to publish in English for international visibility and impact. Notably, 56.7% of SH researchers maintained consistent language practices throughout their careers, suggesting a stable linguistic environment for the majority of the field. When compared to the broader scientific landscape across all disciplines, the data indicates a more conservative shift, with only 24.1% of respondents across all fields reporting increased usage of other languages, while 67.3% maintained consistent language practices.

Figure 60 Changes in language use in reading activities: SH vs. All Disciplines

Language use patterns in scientific reading activities show interesting trends, particularly in SH. Most respondents (59.2% in SH, 71.4% overall) maintain consistent language practices throughout their careers. However, SH researchers show a higher tendency (30%) to adopt non-Italian languages compared to the general scientific population (21.5%). This suggests SH fields may be experiencing greater internationalization or English-language influence in scientific literature.

Figure 61 Language usage in outreach activities: SH vs. All Disciplines

Outreach activities in scientific communication show a strong bilingual pattern, with Italian maintaining a leading role at 86.7% in SH fields, while English usage remains robust at 79.2%. SH researchers demonstrate higher Italian engagement compared to the overall research community; these patterns suggest SH researchers effectively balance international reach through English with robust local communication, reflecting their position bridging global and national research contexts.

Figure 62 Translation rates: SH vs. All Disciplines

Survey results indicate that 35.8% of SH researchers have had their works translated into other languages, while 64.2% have not experienced translation of their outputs. This relatively high translation rate in SH, compared to other disciplines, suggests a field-specific emphasis on making research accessible to diverse linguistic communities and the importance of reaching diverse academic and public audiences.

Figure 63 Usage of generative artificial intelligence tools

Quantitative analysis demonstrates a higher adoption rate of AI language tools within SH disciplines compared to the general scientific population. Specifically, 10% of SH researchers report regular utilization of AI tools for multilingual text production, representing approximately double the adoption rate observed across all disciplines. This elevated usage pattern may be attributed to the particular linguistic demands inherent to SH research, where scholars frequently engage with multiple languages for both content creation and translation tasks.

However, the data also reveals significant resistance to AI tool adoption across all disciplines. Within SH, 46.7% of respondents report no interaction with generative AI tools, a figure that, while substantial, remains lower than the 52.3% observed across all disciplines. The remaining proportion of researchers indicates occasional or experimental usage, suggesting an exploratory approach to these tools rather than full integration into established research practices.

The higher adoption rates in SH may reflect the field's intensive engagement with multilingual communication requirements and its potential openness to technological solutions for addressing these needs. Nevertheless, the substantial proportion of non-users across all disciplines indicates persistent barriers to adoption, potentially relating to concerns about reliability, accuracy, or the appropriate role of AI tools in scientific work.

6.3. Language use evolution: Applied vs. Fundamental Research

Figure 64 Use of languages other than Italian in research activities: Applied vs. Fundamental

The analysis of language usage patterns reveals differences between fundamental and applied research. Research data demonstrates that among researchers primarily engaged in fundamental research, 10.9% exclusively use languages other than Italian, while only 5.4% of those in applied research rely solely on non-Italian languages. The majority in both categories use both Italian and other languages, suggesting a stronger orientation toward international communication in fundamental research, possibly due to its theoretical nature and global relevance.

6.4. Peer reviewed publications in English

Figure 65 Distribution of peer-reviewed publications in English: SH vs. All disciplines

English language dominance in scientific publishing shows remarkable variations across different disciplinary domains, particularly when comparing SH with the broader academic landscape. Analysis of peer-reviewed publication patterns reveals three distinct distribution ranges (0-39%, 40-79%, and 80-100%) that highlight significant divergences in language practices across fields. The empirical data demonstrates a striking contrast: while the vast majority of publications across all disciplines (91.2%) fall within the highest range of English language use (80-100%), SH publications display a markedly different pattern, with only 52.1% in this same range.

This substantial difference becomes even more meaningful when examining the middle range of English language adoption (40-79%), where SH shows a notably higher proportion at 33.3% compared to just 6.7% for all disciplines combined. Similarly, in the lowest range (0-39%), SH maintains a higher percentage of 14.5% versus 2.1% for all disciplines, indicating a more diverse linguistic landscape in these fields.

These distributions warrant deeper interpretation regarding their scientific and cultural implications. The significantly lower proportion of English-language publications in SH likely reflects the intrinsic connection between these disciplines and local cultural contexts. SH often investigates phenomena deeply rooted in specific cultural, linguistic, and social environments, where the use of local languages may be not just preferable, but essential for precise conceptual expression and cultural authenticity. The more balanced distribution across percentage ranges in SH suggests a multilingual approach to knowledge dissemination, possibly indicating a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between language choice and research impact.

From an interpretative perspective, this data reveals a tension between global scientific communication trends and discipline-specific needs. While other fields have largely converged toward English as a lingua franca, SH maintains a more diverse linguistic ecosystem. This resistance to complete English-language dominance might be seen as both a challenge and an asset: while it may limit immediate global visibility, it

preserves crucial cultural nuances and enables more precise communication with local audiences.

6.5 Impact on research funding and collaboration

Figure 66 English language conference participation rates among researchers comfortable with non-Italian language use in grant procedures

The survey results, based on responses from 661 researchers, reveal a striking pattern regarding participation in English-language conferences among respondents who do not feel disadvantaged by Italian language restrictions in bids and grants procedures. An overwhelming majority of respondents (81.5%) report *always* having participated in such conferences throughout their careers. The remaining respondents show varying degrees of engagement, with 8.5% indicating *rare* participation, followed by 5.9% who *sometimes* attend, and 3.8% who *often* participate. Notably, only a minimal fraction (0.3%) reported *never* participating in English-language conferences. These findings suggest that language barriers do not significantly impede conference participation among this specific demographic, as evidenced by the high rate of regular attendance. The data implies that the majority of respondents have successfully integrated international academic engagement into their professional practices, despite operating in a predominantly Italian-speaking scientific environment.

Figure 67 English language conference participation rates among researchers disadvantaged by non-Italian language requirements in funding procedures

The survey data from 199 respondents who report feeling disadvantaged by Italian language restrictions in bids and grants procedures reveals a notably different pattern of participation in English-language conferences. Half of the respondents (50.3%) indicate consistent participation in such conferences throughout their careers, while approximately a quarter (24.6%) report occasional participation. The remaining respondents are fairly evenly distributed between those who *often* participate (11.1%) and those who *rarely* attend (10.6%), with a small proportion (3.5%) *never* participating in English-language conferences.

When comparing these results with the previous data from non-disadvantaged respondents, several striking differences emerge. The most notable contrast is in the proportion of consistent conference participants, which drops from 81.5% among non-disadvantaged respondents to 50.3% among those feeling disadvantaged.

The comparative analysis of these two figures provides evidence that the reported disadvantage in using a language other than Italian – assumed here to be English, as is typically the case – for bids and grants procedures appears to stem from practical language proficiency issues rather than from cultural or ideological resistance to the use of English. This conclusion is strongly supported by the conference participation patterns observed in both groups.

The significantly lower rate of individuals who have *always* participated in English-language conferences among those who feel disadvantaged strongly suggests that practical language barriers, rather than cultural preferences, are the underlying issue. This interpretation is further reinforced by the much higher percentage of respondents who *sometimes* participate in the disadvantaged group (24.6% versus 5.9%), indicating a more hesitant approach to English-language professional environments. These patterns are consistent with behaviour typically associated with language proficiency challenges rather than cultural resistance.

Moreover, the distribution of responses in the disadvantaged group suggests a more cautious engagement with English-language professional activities, characteristic of individuals who may struggle with the language rather than those making a cultural statement. The fact that these researchers participate less frequently in conferences, where active language skills are crucial for networking and presenting research, while

simultaneously reporting difficulties with English in written procedures (bids and grants), points to a comprehensive language proficiency challenge rather than a cultural stance against the use of English in scientific contexts.

6.6. Open-ended responses: Complex dynamics in scientific language practices

The questionnaire included several open-ended questions that provided particularly rich insights into respondents' perspectives on language use in the scientific environment. While these qualitative responses represented a smaller portion of the survey, they revealed nuanced viewpoints and concerns that quantitative data alone could not capture.

A particularly noteworthy observation emerged regarding the potential paradox of multilingualism in scientific contexts. One respondent articulated a thoughtful concern that multilingual practices, contrary to their intended purpose, might actually contribute to research isolation rather than enhancing international visibility. This perspective challenges conventional assumptions about the relationship between linguistic diversity and scientific reach.

The responses also revealed interesting considerations about the evolving landscape of scientific communication. A significant observation emerged regarding the potential emergence of a bilateral linguistic divide in global scientific environment. Specifically, one researcher highlighted the critical need for advanced AI translation capabilities for Chinese scientific literature, suggesting that without such technological advancement, the academic world might bifurcate into two distinct linguistic spheres. This observation points to a possible future scenario where Western researchers could face significant disadvantages in accessing and engaging with Chinese research output.

The open-ended responses also showed the complex pressures shaping language choices in scientific publishing. Researchers consistently described experiencing increasing pressure to publish in English to access high-impact journals and secure competitive funding. This pattern, observed over the past three decades, correlates with a documented decline in Italian-language publications. For instance, the VQR (Research Quality Assessment) 2015-2019 report highlights this shift in the law field¹¹. The survey responses suggest that this shift reflects not merely individual preferences, but rather systematic pressures within the scientific ecosystem.

A final critical theme emerged regarding Italy's international research environment. Responses highlighted how language requirements create barriers to international researcher mobility. The necessity for foreign researchers to acquire Italian proficiency, in addition to maintaining English for international communication, appears to create significant obstacles to attracting diverse international talent. The requirement for Italian language proficiency¹², applicable to public administration positions, also extends to CNR research profiles. This linguistic barrier potentially impacts Italy's competitive position in the global research landscape.

¹¹ Research Quality Assessment 2015-2019 9 (VQR 2015-2019): Final Area Report. Expert Evaluation Group for Area 12- Legal Sciences: https://www.anvur.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/VQR-2015-19_Rapporto_Area_GEV12.pdf.

¹² Art. 3, *Decreto Presidente Consiglio dei Ministri*, February 1994, n. 174.

7. Conclusions

This analysis of language practices and attitudes within the CNR research community reveals a complex and evolving linguistic landscape in Italian scientific research. The results demonstrate a widespread adoption of English across research activities, with the CNR research community showing no notable resistance or discomfort in using languages other than Italian. This openness to multilingual communication, especially within SH disciplines where researchers actively balance Italian with other languages, signals an important evolution in Italy's research landscape.

Key themes emerge from this analysis:

First, the strong positive attitude toward multilingualism (85% of respondents of Q.32(2)) indicates a research community that recognizes the value of linguistic diversity in academic practice. This openness to multilingual communication provides a strong foundation for implementing policies that support and encourage diverse language practices in research.

Second, the identified challenges, particularly the 23% of respondents who feel disadvantaged when working in non-native languages, highlight the urgent need for enhanced institutional support. The varying adoption rates of technological solutions, such as AI-based language tools, suggest opportunities for expanding and improving language support services across disciplines.

Third, variations in language practices within SH across different activities highlight the need for flexible, discipline-sensitive language policies. The higher rates of translation activity in SH (36%) and the growing pressure to publish in English across all fields point to the need for balanced policies that support both international visibility and local research impact.

The key components of a strategic framework encompassing multilingualism in science are outlined in a concentric model (Figure 68) which illustrates the interconnected domains and corresponding action areas for intervention, particularly relevant to the CNR context.

At its core, “Multilingualism in Science” is supported by four fundamental domains:

Linguistic diversity - The range and variety of languages in scientific discourse, their interrelationships, and how they co-exist in research practices

Cultural identity integration - How scientific communities maintain cultural authenticity while participating in global discourse, and how language choices reflect identity

Education and policy - Formal institutional frameworks, training approaches, and governance systems that shape language practices in research

Technology applied to languages - Digital tools, AI solutions, and technological infrastructure supporting multilingual scientific communication.

These fundamental domains are then operationalized through five specific areas for strategic intervention and concrete action.

Assessment Reform addresses the fundamental structures that shape researcher behaviour. This domain advocates for revised metrics that recognize multilingual contributions, integration of criteria valuing research in locally-relevant languages,

and redefinition of “excellence” to acknowledge multilingualism as enhancing scholarly impact rather than diminishing it.

Community Engagement leverages existing language practices within research networks through a bottom-up approach. This domain focuses on mapping institutional language competencies, establishing cross-linguistic knowledge exchange platforms, and developing recognition mechanisms for multilingual research teams, acknowledging that sustainable language policies must emerge from existing community practices.

Support Services reframe language support as enhancement rather than remediation. Interventions include multilingual competency development programs, centralized translation services, and technological solutions facilitating cross-linguistic understanding, treating language resources as fundamental infrastructure for effective scientific exchange.

National Infrastructures balances global integration with local relevance in research ecosystems. This domain encompasses dedicated funding for national journals and databases, institutional multilingual communication policies, and support for open research architectures accommodating multiple languages, recognizing that robust local research infrastructures strengthen global scientific discourse.

Local Language Preservation counteracts linguistic homogenization through dedicated research programs, specialized citation metrics for local-language contributions, and terminological resources maintaining discipline-specific vocabulary in regional languages, ensuring scientific advances remain accessible to local communities while preserving conceptual richness.

The interconnectedness of these intervention areas suggests that isolated initiatives will likely fail to achieve meaningful change. Instead, coordinated engagement across all five domains can create virtuous cycles where progress in one area reinforces advancements in others. By positioning multilingualism as a scientific asset rather than an obstacle, research institutions can simultaneously enhance international visibility and local knowledge dissemination.

Figure 68 Framework for multilingualism in science: core domains and strategic action areas

Looking forward, the success of these initiatives will depend on sustained institutional commitment and regular evaluation of their effectiveness in the Italian context. The positive attitudes toward multilingualism among the CNR research community provide a strong foundation for these changes, but realizing the full potential of linguistic diversity in Italian research will require ongoing attention to evolving needs and challenges. The findings of this survey presented in this Report contribute to the broader dialogue about language practices in Italian scientific research, offering insights that may be valuable beyond the national context.

Appendix

The Appendix includes:

- a) The Italian version of the invitation email to the questionnaire, originally sent on June 27, 2024, as well as the reminder email distributed on July 24, 2024, to the CNR mailing list addressed to researchers and technologists;
- b) The full Italian text of the questionnaire.

Text of the Invitation Emails

 Invito a partecipare a Indagine CoARA su Multilinguismo e valutazione della ricerca 27 giugno 2024 16:07

Da: [Indagine CNR sul multilinguismo per CoARA](#)

A: [ricercatori tecnologi](#)

Cc: [Ginevra Peruginelli](#)

Care colleghe, cari colleghi,

L'Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari (IGSG) vi invita a partecipare all'indagine in tema di **multilinguismo e pregiudizi linguistici nella valutazione della ricerca scientifica**.

L'indagine si colloca all'interno dell'iniziativa CoARA - *Coalizione per l'avanzamento della valutazione della ricerca* ed è una delle attività previste dal CoARA Working Group "Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment".

Si tratta del primo passo per esplorare la percezione della comunità scientifica del CNR sul multilinguismo nelle pratiche di ricerca e mira a indagare come la diversità linguistica sia percepita nelle attività di ricerca e nella loro valutazione.

Vi chiediamo gentilmente di compilare il questionario disponibile al seguente link:

<https://www.indagini.irpps.cnr.it/index.php?r=survey/index&sid=475524&lang=it>

La scadenza per la compilazione è il **9 agosto 2024**; il tempo necessario per rispondere alle domande è di circa 10 minuti.

Il questionario è anonimo.

Vi ringraziamo per il supporto: la vostra partecipazione è essenziale.

Con i più cari saluti,

Ginevra Peruginelli e Sebastiano Faro

IGSG-CNR, CoARA WG "Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment" - TF2 Landscape analysis

 PROMEMORIA - Invito a partecipare a Indagine CoARA su Multilinguismo e valutazione della ricerca 24 luglio 2024 11:46

Da: [Indagine CNR sul multilinguismo per CoARA](#)

A: [ricercatori-tecnologi](#)

Care colleghe, cari colleghi,

Ricordiamo che è ancora possibile partecipare all'indagine in tema di **multilinguismo e pregiudizi linguistici nella valutazione della ricerca scientifica**. L'indagine si colloca all'interno dell'iniziativa **CoARA** - Coalizione per l'avanzamento della valutazione della ricerca ed è una delle attività previste dal CoARA Working Group "Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment".

Il questionario è disponibile al seguente link:

<https://www.indagini.irpps.cnr.it/index.php?r=survey/index&sid=475524&lang=it>

La scadenza per la compilazione è il **9 agosto 2024**.

Grazie. Con i più cari saluti,

Ginevra Peruginelli e Sebastiano Faro

IGSG-CNR, CoARA WG "Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment" - TF2 Landscape analysis

Questionario in tema di Multilinguismo e pregiudizi linguistici nella valutazione della ricerca

CoARA è la [Coalizione per l'avanzamento della valutazione della ricerca](#), di cui fanno parte università, enti finanziatori, autorità nazionali e regionali e società scientifiche e di ricercatori che hanno firmato l'[Accordo sulla Riforma della Valutazione della Ricerca \(ARRA\)](#). CoARA include le organizzazioni coinvolte nel processo di valutazione della ricerca per facilitare lo scambio di informazioni e buone pratiche e avviare una riforma complessiva del sistema di valutazione della ricerca. Il Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) che ha firmato l'ARRA è anche co-coordinatore del Capitolo Italiano di CoARA.

Il questionario qui proposto è stato sviluppato dall'[Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari \(IGSG-CNR\)](#) che fa parte del gruppo di lavoro CoARA "Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment" e tecnicamente realizzato dall'[Istituto di Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali \(IRPPS-CNR\)](#). Si tratta del primo passo per esplorare la percezione del multilinguismo nelle pratiche di ricerca nei vari settori scientifici; destinato alla comunità scientifica del CNR, mira a indagare come la diversità linguistica sia percepita nelle attività di ricerca e nella loro valutazione.

Indicazioni per la compilazione del questionario

Il questionario considera l'italiano come lingua di riferimento per gli intervistati. In particolare, le domande hanno per oggetto le attività di ricerca svolte dalle ricercatrici e ricercatori e includono diverse competenze quali la redazione di testi, l'interazione orale, la lettura/studio, l'insegnamento e la comunicazione/divulgazione dei risultati della ricerca.

Trattamento dei dati personali

Il questionario è anonimo e non si richiedono informazioni che consentano l'identificazione del partecipante. Se è stato usato un codice di accesso per accedere a quest'indagine, questo codice non sarà registrato assieme alle risposte fornite. Il codice partecipante è gestito in un database diverso e viene aggiornato soltanto per indicare se è stata completata (o no) l'indagine. Non c'è nessun modo per abbinare i codici di accesso alle risposte all'indagine. I dati raccolti e la loro analisi in forma aggregata saranno pubblicati su Zenodo.

Vi ringraziamo per l'aiuto che vorrete dare a questa indagine!

Ci sono 48 domande in questa indagine.

Domande introduttive

D01. Indica il tuo livello professionale *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Ricercatrice/Ricercatore
- Tecnologa/Tecnologo
- Prima ricercatrice/primo ricercatore
- Prima tecnologa/primo tecnologo
- Dirigente di ricerca
- Dirigente tecnologo

D02. Qual é la tua fascia d'età? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- < 30
- 31-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- >60

D03. Indica il genere con cui ti identifichi *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Donna
- Uomo
- Non binario
- Preferisco non rispondere

D04. Indica gli anni di attività scientifica *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- 1-9 anni
- 10-20 anni
- 21-30 anni
- più di 30 anni

D05. Qual é l'ambito scientifico delle tue ricerche

*

Selezionare al massimo 2 risposte

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- PE1 Mathematics - All areas of mathematics, pure and applied, plus mathematical foundations of computer science, mathematical physics and statistics
- PE2 Fundamental Constituents of Matter - Particle, nuclear, plasma, atomic, molecular, gas, and optical physics
- PE3 Condensed Matter Physics - Structure, electronic properties, fluids, nanosciences, biological physics
- PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences - Analytical chemistry, chemical theory, physical chemistry/chemical physics
- PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials - New materials and new synthetic approaches, structure-properties relations, solid state chemistry, molecular architecture, organic chemistry
- PE6 Computer Science and Informatics - Informatics and information systems, computer science, scientific computing, intelligent systems
- PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering - Electrical, electronic, communication, optical and systems engineering
- PE8 Products and Processes Engineering - Product and process design, chemical, civil, environmental, mechanical, vehicle engineering, energy processes and relevant computational methods
- PE9 Universe Sciences - Astro-physics/-chemistry/-biology; solar system; planetary systems; stellar, galactic and extragalactic astronomy; cosmology; space sciences; astronomical instrumentation and data
- PE10 Earth System Science - Physical geography, geology, geophysics, atmospheric sciences, oceanography, climatology, cryology, ecology, global environmental change, biogeochemical cycles, natural resources management
- PE11 Materials Engineering - Advanced materials development: performance enhancement, modelling, large-scale preparation, modification, tailoring, optimisation, novel and combined use of materials, etc.
- LS1 Molecules of Life: Biological Mechanisms, Structures and Functions - Molecular biology, biochemistry, structural biology, molecular biophysics, synthetic and chemical biology, drug design, innovative methods and modelling
- LS2 Integrative Biology: from Genes and Genomes to Systems - Genetics, epigenetics, genomics and other 'omics studies, bioinformatics, systems biology, genetic

diseases, gene editing, innovative methods and modelling, 'omics for personalised medicine

LS3 Cell Biology, Development, Stem Cells and Regeneration - Structure and function of the cell, cell-cell communication, embryogenesis, tissue differentiation, organogenesis, growth, development, evolution of development, organoids, stem cells, regeneration, therapeutic approaches

LS4 Physiology in Health, Disease and Ageing - Organ and tissue physiology, comparative physiology, physiology of ageing, pathophysiology, inter organ and tissue communication, endocrinology, nutrition, metabolism, interaction with the microbiome, non-communicable diseases including cancer (and except disorders of the nervous system and immunity-related diseases)

LS5 Neuroscience and Disorders of the Nervous System - Nervous system development, homeostasis and ageing, nervous system function and dysfunction, systems neuroscience and modelling, biological basis of cognitive processes and of behaviour, neurological and mental disorders

LS6 Immunity, Infection and Immunotherapy - The immune system, related disorders and their mechanisms, biology of infectious agents and infection, biological basis of prevention and treatment of infectious diseases, innovative immunological tools and approaches, including therapies

LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases - Medical technologies and tools for prevention, diagnosis and treatment of human diseases, therapeutic approaches and interventions, pharmacology, preventative medicine, epidemiology and public health, digital medicine

LS8 Environmental Biology, Ecology and Evolution - Ecology, biodiversity, environmental change, evolutionary biology, behavioural ecology, microbial ecology, marine biology, ecophysiology, theoretical developments and modelling

LS9 Biotechnology and Biosystems Engineering - Biotechnology using all organisms, biotechnology for environment and food applications, applied plant and animal sciences, bioengineering and synthetic biology, biomass and biofuels, biohazards

SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations - Economics, finance, management

SH2 Institutions, Governance and Legal Systems - Political science, international relations, law

SH3 The Social World and Its Interactions - Sociology, social psychology, education sciences, communication studies

SH4 The Human Mind and Its Complexity - Cognitive science, psychology, linguistics

SH5 Texts and Concepts - Literary studies, literature, philosophy

SH6 The Study of the Human Past - Archaeology and history

SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space - Human geography, demography, health, sustainability science, territorial planning, spatial analysis

SH8 Studies of Cultures and Arts - Social anthropology, studies of cultures, studies of arts

Selezionare massimo due settori di ricerca ERC prevalenti

D06. Indica il tipo (o i tipi) di ricerca che svolgi e il relativo impegno in percentuale? *

Inserire una percentuale

Ricerca di base

Ricerca applicata

Sviluppo sperimentale

La somma deve essere pari a 100

D07. L'italiano è la tua lingua madre? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

Sì

No

D08. Quali lingue diverse dalla tua lingua madre conosci e qual è il tuo livello di conoscenza? *

Scegliere la risposta appropriata per ciascun elemento:

	Utente base (PreA1, A1, A2)	Utente autonomo (B1, B2)	Utente avanzato (C1, C2)	Non conosco
bulgaro	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ceco	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
croato	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
danese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
estone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
finlandese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
francese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
greco	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
inglese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
irlandese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
italiano	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
lettone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
lituano	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
maltese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
neerlandese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
polacco	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Utente base (PreA1, A1, A2)	Utente autonomo (B1, B2)	Utente avanzato (C1, C2)	Non conosco
portoghese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
rumeno	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
slovacco	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
sloveno	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
spagnolo	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
tedesco	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
svedese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ungherese	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
altra lingua	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Indicare al massimo cinque lingue. Il livello di conoscenze fa riferimento agli indicatori previsti dal [Quadro comune europeo di riferimento per le lingue](#)

Uso delle lingue nelle attività di ricerca

D09. Usi lingue diverse dall'italiano nello svolgimento della tua attività di ricerca? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì, uso l'italiano e altre lingue
- Sì, uso solo altre lingue
- No, uso solo l'italiano

D09a. Perché non usi lingue diverse dall'italiano? *

Selezionare tutte quelle che corrispondono

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- Perché nel mio campo l'italiano è una lingua utilizzata dalla comunità di ricerca internazionale.
- Perché non mi sento sicuro/a in altre lingue.
- Perché non è necessario per la mia carriera.
- Perché non partecipo ad attività che richiedono specificamente l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano.
- Perché sono specificamente interessato/a a condividere i risultati della mia ricerca con i ricercatori italiani, il pubblico in generale e/o i responsabili politici in Italia.
- Perché l'italiano è la mia lingua madre e ritengo che rinunciare alla propria lingua sia un regresso culturale.
- Perché la mia ricerca è focalizzata sull'Italia ed è di interesse soprattutto per gli italofoeni.
- Altro:

D09b. È percezione comune che in diversi contesti (ad esempio, l'insegnamento, le procedure di finanziamento, gli esercizi di valutazione) ci sia, in Italia, una crescente richiesta di utilizzo della lingua inglese: esprimi il tuo grado di accordo rispetto alle seguenti affermazioni *

Scegliere la risposta appropriata per ciascun elemento:

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
Una crescente richiesta di utilizzo della lingua inglese in un mondo globalizzato è inevitabile e corrisponde a una vera e propria necessità	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Una crescente richiesta di utilizzo della lingua inglese non sembra giustificata da ragioni valide	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Considero una crescente richiesta di utilizzo della lingua inglese un danno per la cultura e la scienza italiana	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Uso delle lingue diverse dall'italiano nelle attività di ricerca

Questo set di domande è dedicato a te che usi anche o solo lingue diverse dall'italiano e si concentra su attività specifiche che svolgi in quanto ricercatrice/ricercatore. Per aiutarti a rispondere al questionario, di seguito vengono proposte alcune definizioni:

Redazione di testi: Creazione di contenuti scientifici, come libri, capitoli di libro, articoli, relazioni e ogni altro testo scritto che documenti i risultati delle attività di ricerca e contribuisca alla discussione scientifica.

Interazione orale: Comunicazione verbale in presentazioni, seminari e riunioni per condividere i risultati della ricerca all'interno della comunità scientifica, per collaborare con i colleghi, per comunicare e interagire con gli enti che erogano finanziamenti e con le parti interessate alle attività di ricerca.

Lettura: Studio e analisi critica di lavori scientifici.

Insegnamento: Diffusione della conoscenza attraverso l'istruzione formale, compresa la progettazione di corsi, l'organizzazione di lezioni e il tutoraggio degli studenti.

Divulgazione (orale o scritta): Condivisione dei risultati della ricerca in contesti diversi dal mondo scientifico attraverso vari canali (pubblicazioni divulgative, presentazioni, materiali informativi...).

Inoltre, due domande sono dedicate alle specifiche attività di redazione di proposte progettuali da sottoporre agli enti finanziatori.

D10. Quale lingua diversa dall'italiano utilizzi principalmente in tutti gli aspetti del tuo lavoro di ricerca? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Se si sceglie 'Altro:', specificare la scelta fatta nel campo testo di accompagnamento.

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- bulgaro
- ceco
- croato
- danese
- estone
- finlandese
- francese
- greco
- inglese
- irlandese
- lettone
- lituano
- maltese
- neerlandese
- polacco
- portoghese
- rumeno
- slovacco
- sloveno
- spagnolo
- tedesco
- svedese
- ungherese
- Altro

D11. Quale/i lingua/e hai usato nella tua attività di *redazione di testi* negli ultimi cinque anni e in che percentuale hai usato ciascuna lingua? *

Inserire la percentuale di utilizzo

bulgaro

ceco

croato

danese

estone

finlandese

francese

greco

inglese

irlandese

italiano

lettone

lituano

maltese

Inserire la percentuale di utilizzo

neerlandese

polacco

portoghese

rumeno

slovacco

sloveno

spagnolo

tedesco

svedese

ungherese

altra lingua

Per **redazione di testi** intendiamo: Creazione di contenuti scientifici, come libri, capitoli di libro, articoli, relazioni e ogni altro testo scritto che documenti i risultati delle attività di ricerca e contribuisca alla discussione scientifica.

Indicare al massimo cinque lingue. Il totale deve essere pari a 100.

D11a. Come è cambiato l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nella tua attività di *redazione di testi* nel corso della tua carriera? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Ho usato costantemente la stessa lingua (o le stesse lingue) per tutta la mia carriera
- Con il tempo ho iniziato a preferire l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano
- In passato usavo più frequentemente lingue diverse dall'italiano, ma tale uso è diminuito con il tempo
- Non sono in grado di descrivere in modo chiaro come sia cambiato il mio uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nel corso della mia carriera

D12. Quale/i lingua/e hai usato nella tua attività di *interazione orale* negli ultimi cinque anni e in che percentuale hai usato ciascuna lingua? *

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

bulgaro

ceco

croato

danese

estone

finlandese

francese

greco

inglese

irlandese

italiano

lettone

lituano

maltese

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

neerlandese

polacco

portoghese

rumeno

slovacco

sloveno

spagnolo

tedesco

svedese

ungherese

altra lingua

Per **interazione orale** intendiamo: Comunicazione verbale in presentazioni, seminari e riunioni per condividere i risultati della ricerca all'interno della comunità scientifica per collaborare con i colleghi, per comunicare e interagire con gli enti che erogano finanziamenti e con le parti interessate alle attività di ricerca.

Indicare al massimo cinque lingue. Il totale deve essere pari a 100.

D12a. Come si è modificato o è cambiato l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nella tua attività di *interazione orale* nel corso della tua carriera? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Ho usato costantemente la stessa lingua (o le stesse lingue) per tutta la mia carriera
- Con il tempo ho iniziato a preferire l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano
- In passato usavo più frequentemente lingue diverse dall'italiano, ma tale uso è diminuito con il tempo
- Non sono in grado di descrivere in modo chiaro come sia cambiato il mio uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nel corso della mia carriera

D13. Quale/i lingua/e hai usato nella tua attività di *lettura* negli ultimi cinque anni e in che percentuale hai usato ciascuna lingua? *

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

bulgaro

ceco

croato

danese

estone

finlandese

francese

greco

inglese

irlandese

italiano

lettone

lituano

maltese

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

neerlandese

polacco

portoghese

rumeno

slovacco

sloveno

spagnolo

tedesco

svedese

ungherese

altra lingua

Per **lettura** intendiamo: Studio e analisi critica di lavori scientifici.

Indicare al massimo cinque lingue. Il totale deve essere pari a 100.

D13a. Come si è modificato o è cambiato l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nella tua attività di *lettura* nel corso della tua carriera? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Ho usato costantemente la stessa lingua (o le stesse lingue) per tutta la mia carriera
- Con il tempo ho iniziato a preferire l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano
- In passato usavo più frequentemente lingue diverse dall'italiano, ma tale uso è diminuito con il tempo
- Non sono in grado di descrivere in modo chiaro come sia cambiato il mio uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nel corso della mia carriera

D14. Hai svolto attività di *insegnamento* negli ultimi cinque anni? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì
- No

Per **insegnamento** intendiamo: diffusione della conoscenza attraverso l'istruzione formale, compresa la progettazione di corsi, l'organizzazione di lezioni e il tutoraggio degli studenti.

D14a. Quale/i lingua/e hai usato nella tua attività di *insegnamento* negli ultimi cinque anni e in che percentuale hai usato ciascuna lingua? *

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

bulgaro

ceco

croato

danese

estone

finlandese

francese

greco

inglese

irlandese

italiano

lettone

lituano

maltese

Inserisci la percentuale di utilizzo

neerlandese

polacco

portoghese

rumeno

slovacco

sloveno

spagnolo

tedesco

svedese

ungherese

altra lingua

Indicare al massimo cinque lingue. Il totale deve essere pari a 100.

D14b. Come si è modificato o è cambiato l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nella tua attività di *insegnamento* nel corso della tua carriera? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Ho usato costantemente la stessa lingua (o le stesse lingue) per tutta la mia carriera
- Con il tempo ho iniziato a preferire l'uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano
- In passato usavo più frequentemente lingue diverse dall'italiano, ma tale uso è diminuito con il tempo
- Non sono in grado di descrivere in modo chiaro come sia cambiato il mio uso di lingue diverse dall'italiano nel corso della mia carriera
- Non ho mai svolto attività di insegnamento nel corso della mia carriera

D15. Quale/i lingua/e utilizzi quando ti impegni in attività di *divulgazione (esposizione orale)*? *

Selezionare tutte quelle che corrispondono

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- bulgaro
- ceco
- croato
- danese
- estone
- finlandese
- francese
- greco
- inglese
- irlandese
- italiano
- lettone
- lituano
- maltese
- neerlandese
- polacco
- portoghese
- rumeno
- slovacco
- sloveno
- spagnolo
- tedesco
- svedese
- ungherese

Altro:

Per **Divulgazione (orale o scritta)** intendiamo: Condivisione dei risultati della ricerca in contesti diversi dal mondo scientifico attraverso vari canali (pubblicazioni divulgative, presentazioni, materiali informativi...).

D16. Quale/i lingua/e utilizzi quando ti impegni in attività di *divulgazione* (*produzione di testi scritti*)? *

Selezionare tutte quelle che corrispondono

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- bulgaro
- ceco
- croato
- danese
- estone
- finlandese
- francese
- greco
- inglese
- irlandese
- italiano
- lettone
- lituano
- maltese
- neerlandese
- polacco
- portoghese
- rumeno
- slovacco
- sloveno
- spagnolo
- tedesco
- svedese
- ungherese

Altro:

D17. Quanto è difficile per te comunicare in italiano al di fuori del mondo accademico i risultati delle ricerche prodotti in lingue diverse dall'italiano? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- 1. Non comporta nessuna difficoltà
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5. Comporta grande difficoltà

D18. La richiesta di utilizzare una lingua diversa dall'italiano ti impedisce di partecipare a procedure di finanziamento? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì, non partecipo
- No, partecipo
- No, partecipo ma richiedo il supporto della mia struttura

D19. Ritieni di essere svantaggiato se sei obbligato a utilizzare una lingua diversa dall'italiano per partecipare a procedure per la richiesta di finanziamenti? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì
- No

D20. Hai pubblicato testi che sono stati tradotti in lingua diversa dall'originale? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

Sì

No

D20a. Se le tue pubblicazioni sono state tradotte, indica in quale(i) lingua(e)

*

Selezionare tutte quelle che corrispondono

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- bulgaro
- ceco
- croato
- danese
- estone
- finlandese
- francese
- greco
- inglese
- irlandese
- italiano
- lettone
- lituano
- maltese
- neerlandese
- polacco
- portoghese
- rumeno
- slovacco
- sloveno
- spagnolo
- tedesco
- svedese
- ungherese

Altro:

D20b. Quali sono le ragioni principali che hanno portato alla traduzione dei tuoi testi? *

Selezionare tutte quelle che corrispondono

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- Iniziativa personale
- Richiesta da parte di colleghi
- Richiesta da parte di riviste o curatori di opere collettanee
- Richiesta da parte di editori
- Richiesta da parte dei finanziatori

Altro:

D21. Nella tua attività di ricerca utilizzi strumenti di traduzione automatica (ad esempio, Google Translate, DeepL)? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì, utilizzo questi strumenti
- Sì, li utilizzo in una certa misura
- Non ancora, perchè non li considero abbastanza affidabili
- No, non uso questi strumenti e non li userò in futuro

D21a. Se utilizzi strumenti di traduzione automatica, con quale frequenza li usi quando leggi? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Spesso
- Qualche volta
- Raramente

D21b. Se utilizzi strumenti di traduzione automatica, con quale frequenza li usi quando scrivi? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Spesso
- Qualche volta
- Raramente

D22. Utilizzi strumenti di intelligenza artificiale generativa (ad esempio ChatGPT) per produrre testi in varie lingue? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì, utilizzo regolarmente questi strumenti per la produzione di testi in varie lingue
- Ho sperimentato questi strumenti per la produzione di testi in varie lingue, ma non li ho integrati completamente nelle mie pratiche di lavoro
- No, non ho mai sperimentato questi strumenti

Uso della lingua inglese

Questa sezione è dedicata a coloro che hanno risposto di essere di madrelingua italiana.

D23. Quando usi la lingua inglese, perchè lo fai? *

Scegliere **tutte** le corrispondenti:

- è la lingua franca del mio campo di ricerca
- garantisce visibilità internazionale
- è necessario per collaborare con ricercatrici e ricercatori stranieri
- ho maggiore familiarità con la terminologia inglese
- le riviste di mio interesse accettano manoscritti solo in inglese
- è necessario per ottenere un finanziamento o una posizione di ricerca
- presumo che i lavori in inglese siano valutati meglio
- non uso mai l'inglese

Altro:

D24. Come descriveresti la distribuzione dei tuoi manoscritti sottoposti a peer-review nel corso della tua carriera, distinguendo tra quelli in inglese e quelli in lingue diverse dall'inglese? *

Distribuzione percentuale

Manoscritti in inglese (%)

Manoscritti in altre lingue (%)

Il totale deve essere uguale a 100.

D25. Come descriveresti la distribuzione delle tue partecipazioni a convegni sul tuo specifico campo di ricerca nel corso della tua carriera, distinguendo tra quelli in inglese e quelli in lingue diverse dall'inglese? *

Distribuzione percentuale

Convegni in inglese (%)

Convegni in altre lingue (%)

Il totale deve essere uguale a 100.

D26. Con quale frequenza ti è capitato di non partecipare a un convegno in lingua inglese (per presentare la tua ricerca o semplicemente per assistere) perché non ti sentivi abbastanza sicura/o nel comunicare in inglese? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sempre (non ho mai partecipato)
- Spesso
- Qualche volta
- Raramente
- Mai (ho sempre partecipato)

D27. Qual è la tua posizione rispetto alla politica linguistica delle riviste che pubblicano esclusivamente in lingua inglese? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- La rivista ha la priorità sulla richiesta dell'uso esclusivo della lingua inglese
- Pubblico solo su riviste che accettano contributi in varie lingue
- Non considero mai la richiesta di utilizzare la lingua inglese un problema
- Altro

D28. Ti è mai capitato che un tuo manoscritto sia stato rifiutato da una rivista in lingua inglese per l'insufficiente qualità della lingua? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Sì
- No

D29. Qual è la percentuale delle tue pubblicazioni redatte in inglese per le quali hai pagato un servizio professionale per migliorare la qualità della lingua? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

- Non ho mai fatto pubblicazioni in inglese
- 0%
- 1-25%
- 26-50%
- 51-75%
- 76-100%

La visione della comunità scientifica su multilinguismo e valutazione

D30. Qual è la tua opinione riguardo alle seguenti affermazioni sulla scelta della lingua e sulle pratiche di valutazione?

La mia scelta di utilizzare una determinata lingua è influenzata dalla considerazione che:

*

Scegliere la risposta appropriata per ciascun elemento:

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
nelle procedure di reclutamento/promozione in Italia, potrebbero essere preferite determinate lingue.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
nelle procedure di finanziamento dei progetti in Italia, potrebbero essere preferite determinate lingue.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
nell'esercizio nazionale di valutazione (VQR), potrebbero essere preferite determinate lingue.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
nelle procedure di reclutamento e finanziamento dei progetti all'estero, potrebbero essere preferite determinate lingue.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
le convenzioni accademiche impongono di	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
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utilizzare determinate lingue per comunicare efficacemente i risultati di ricerca.

la massimizzazione dell'impatto e dell'accessibilità della ricerca a livello globale richiede di utilizzare determinate lingue.

<input type="radio"/>				
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D31. Hai mai ricevuto una valutazione negativa da parte di una commissione di valutazione per non aver incluso pubblicazioni in altre lingue oltre l'italiano in una tua domanda? *

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Scegli **solo una** delle seguenti:

Sì

No

D32. Qual è la tua opinione riguardo alle seguenti affermazioni sull'uso di una lingua diversa dalla propria e sul rapporto con la libertà accademica?

*

Scegliere la risposta appropriata per ciascun elemento:

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
L'obbligo di utilizzare una lingua diversa dalla propria potrebbe potenzialmente limitare la capacità di esprimere idee complesse in modo efficace.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Riconosco che l'uso di lingue diverse dalla propria può presentare delle sfide, ma lo considero un'opportunità di crescita intellettuale e di collaborazione globale, piuttosto che una minaccia alla libertà accademica.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
Credo che la libertà accademica si estenda alla scelta della lingua, e dovrebbe consentire di non rinunciare all'uso della propria lingua nel perseguimento della conoscenza e dello scambio scientifico.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D33. Qual è la tua opinione in merito alle seguenti affermazioni sulla prevalenza di pubblicazioni in lingua inglese nelle banche dati citazionali? *

Scegliere la risposta appropriata per ciascun elemento:

	Pienamente d'accordo	D'accordo	Neutrale	Non d'accordo	Per niente d'accordo
Se da un lato la prevalenza di pubblicazioni in lingua inglese nelle banche dati citazionali è vantaggiosa per la diffusione globale della ricerca, dall'altro può emarginare i ricercatori non anglofoni e i loro contributi.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
La prevalenza di pubblicazioni in lingua inglese nelle banche dati citazionali sottolinea la necessità di maggiori sforzi per promuovere il multilinguismo e l'inclusività nella comunicazione accademica.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Le banche dati citazionali che presentano principalmente pubblicazioni in lingua inglese possono perpetuare pregiudizi linguistici e ostacolare la visibilità di ricerche	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pienamente
d'accordo D'accordo Neutrale Non
d'accordo d'accordo Per
niente
d'accordo

importanti condotte in
lingue diverse
dall'inglese.

Le pubblicazioni in
lingua inglese nelle
banche dati citazionali
rappresentano
l'eccellenza
internazionale e
consentono di
misurare l'impatto
scientifico globale.

Fine del questionario

Hai raggiunto la fine del questionario. Grazie per la tua partecipazione!

Se desideri lascia un commento: la tua opinione è preziosa per la nostra analisi!

Premi INVIA per concludere.

Scrivere la propria risposta qui:

Inviare l'indagine.

Grazie per aver completato il questionario.

CoARA Working Group on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment

Part of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), this Working Group aims to explore and address language-related biases in research evaluation. The group advocates for fair, inclusive, and multilingual research assessment practices across Europe and beyond.

IGSG-CNR (Report coordination)

The Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) is a multidisciplinary institute, combining legal, social, and technological expertise. It conducts research on the impact of digital innovation on law, legal systems, and justice, with a focus on ICT, AI, legal data, and e-justice. The Institute supports public institutions through applied research, technology transfer, and international collaboration.

IRPPS-CNR

The Istituto di Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) conducts interdisciplinary research on population trends, migration, welfare policies, and the societal impact of knowledge and information technologies.